

Narratives, Scenarios and Models of Fair Ambition

Proceedings of an Informal Seminar Series

7 April 2026

Suggested citation: Fair Ambition Seminars (2026) *Informal Seminars on Narratives, Scenarios and Models of Fair Ambition. Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19453806>

Table of contents

Context of the Seminar Series.....	1
Equity and Justice in Adaptation	4
Equity under Condition of “Overshoot”	5
Equity in Climate Finance	7
Equity and Ambition in Global IAMs and Various Applications.....	9
Fair Shares and National Emissions Pathways.....	11
Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) and Fair Ambition.....	13
Equity in Distributing the Benefits of Decarbonization.....	14
Climate Policy and Distributive Justice: Philosophical Perspectives on Equity	15
Narratives of Equity and Their Role in Processes.....	17
Climate Litigation and the ICJ Advisory Opinion	18
International Environment Law Principles and Quantified Fair Shares.....	20
Moral and Political Philosophy	21
Narrative Writing Workshop	23
How Scenarios Are Used	24
Appendix – Discussion Papers Prepared for the Seminar Series.....	27

Context of the Seminar Series

An informal seminar series on “Scenarios, Narratives and Modelling of Fair Ambition” was held over the course of 2024-2025. The aim was to generate a more shared understanding of complex issues of equity and ambition among the participants, and to do so in an atmosphere that fostered trust and enabled frank and open conversations. The scope of discussions was intentionally broad, as is evident in the topics of seminar sessions. The approximately 35 participants came from a range of different perspectives, communities of practice and geographies. Explicitly, the seminars were not intended to generate agreement among participants but aimed instead at generating deeper understanding of divergent perspectives and at learning from each other. The overall framing included quantitative analysis, such as modeling, and qualitative analysis, drawing on philosophy, law and other disciplines. Seminars were held virtually and at a four-day in-person symposium. The Chatham House Rule was applied, to ensure that participants could facilitate open discussion. The Chatham House Rule stipulates that “... participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed.” It is in the spirit of this rule and to facilitate such use of the information and views shared during the seminars that these proceedings have been prepared. And, therefore, no names of participants (including those who authored the discussion papers in the appendix) have been included in these proceedings.

These proceedings aim to distill intellectual output for a broader audience and for participants. They are not, and cannot be, comprehensive as the discussions were free-flowing and generative. They capture key insights, learning from creative tensions across different perspectives and – where they emerged – more shared understandings. One of the intentions of the overall seminar series is that participants will carry these

learnings into back into their diverse communities of practice – these proceedings are intended to assist with that. Many problems and challenges were identified and debated, several unresolved, yet some specific ideas to address identified challenges and contribute to improved analysis of fair ambition. We as participants hope that these proceedings may be useful to others.

These proceedings have been prepared by the convenors of this seminar series – Harald Winkler and Andrew Marquard (both University of Cape Town) and Ceecee Holz (Climate Equity Reference Project) –, based on notes and session summaries that convenors and participants serving as note-takers and facilitators had prepared and whose contributions are gratefully acknowledged. The convenors issue these proceedings their own authority: in other words, even though participants agreed with the release of these proceedings and were given opportunities to review them, the responsibility for any remaining unintentional errors, omissions, and misrepresentations is solely that of the convenors. These proceedings intend to summarize the rich conversations of the seminar series. As stated above, it was not the purpose of the seminar series to generate agreement between participants and as such, these proceedings should not be understood as expressing views that are agreed to by the participants, rather, they are views that were expressed and discussed by participants in the course of the series. Some seminar sessions benefitted from discussion papers that were prepared by participants as inputs to the sessions; these are attached as appendices.

Equity and Justice in Adaptation

Discussions centred on how adaptation equity and justice affect and are affected by limits to adaptation, distinguishing between hard adaptation limits and socially-driven “soft” limits that are often rooted in inequality – vulnerability reflects structural injustices, not just physical thresholds. Participants examined who is excluded from adaptation processes and how poorly designed interventions may reinforce or create new limits. On the other hand, adaptation processes that embrace capabilities-based approaches that link adaptation to human freedom and development, capture lived realities and center agency-focused narratives were seen as key to advancing equitable adaptation.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Justice Within Limits: Climate Futures and Adaptive Capacity.”

A distinction between hard and soft adaptation limits reveals how climate vulnerability is shaped not only by physical thresholds but also by social and structural injustices. A distinction was drawn between *hard* and *soft* adaptation limits. Hard limits, or limits *of* adaptation, denote thresholds beyond which climate impacts overwhelm the possibility of further adjustment, largely determined by global mitigation pathways. Soft limits, or limits *to* adaptation, refer to situations where adaptation becomes increasingly difficult or ineffective due to constraints such as insufficient resources, weak governance, or social and political marginalization. Participants highlighted that soft limits are not simply technical barriers but can be manifestations of deeper structural injustices that constrain people’s freedoms to adapt on their own terms. “Maladaptation,” especially when driven by ad-hoc, siloed or top-down measures, can entrench these injustices and accelerate the crossing of soft limits.

Justice in adaptation, when assessed through the lens of human capabilities, links climate responses to broader development and wellbeing. Building on Amartya Sen’s work,¹ participants discussed justice not in terms of resources or outcomes, but in terms of the freedoms that people have to live the kind of lives they value. This framing links adaptation directly to the right to development and to well-being, highlighting that adaptation is inseparable from development pathways. Embedding a capabilities approach into adaptation research and policy could help move beyond narrow, technical metrics of adaptive capacity towards a justice-focused understanding of agency and opportunity.

Participants also debated how equity and justice are represented or omitted in models of climate and development futures. The question was raised not only whether integrated assessment models (IAMs) capture adaptation adequately, but whether they capture development at all. When IAMs treat adaptive capacity through indicators such as income or education, they risk obscuring political, historical and structural constraints on people’s freedoms. While some noted ongoing efforts to improve spatial resolution and sectoral integration, others cautioned that global and national-level models still fail to reflect the lived realities and regional dynamics that determine adaptation outcomes.

Constructing narratives that emphasize agency and capability are key tools to advance equity in adaptation. Across discussions, participants emphasized the need for constructive narratives of adaptation justice: narratives that recognize agency, power and capability rather than reiterating injustice. Equity in adaptation requires attention to who can adapt and who faces limitations to adaptation, who makes

1 E.g., Amartya Sen (1989) "Development as Capability Expansion" in *Journal of Development Planning*, 41–58; Amartya Sen (1999) *Development as Freedom*. Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press; Amartya Sen (2004) "Capabilities, Lists, and Public Reason: Continuing the Conversation" in *Feminist Economics*, 10(3), 77–80. [doi: 10.1080/1354570042000315163]

relevant decisions (and how), and under what conditions can people meaningfully shape their adaptive responses to climate change.²

Equity under Condition of “Overshoot”

Participants agreed that exceeding 1.5°C of warming is now unavoidable with uncertain prospects for returning below it. Discussions considered the risks and benefits of shifting narratives from equity under specific temperature goals toward those that emphasize equitable, people-centered development and clearer risk communication. New narratives should stress urgency and integrate climate and development goals. Strengthening understanding of the conditions of development, adaptation and impacts in an overshoot world, and developing new capabilities of such understanding is critical in a warming world with escalating risks.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Hope is not a strategy...a practitioner’s viewpoint.”

Acknowledging the reality that 1.5°C will soon be exceeded and we will be starting to face the implications of overshoot. The IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report established that limiting warming to 1.5°C “without overshoot” is no longer plausible – at this point, we can be almost certain that warming of 1.5°C will be exceeded, due to insufficient efforts. Furthermore, while exceed-and-return (“overshoot”) pathways are still plausible, they are not consistent with current levels of mitigation effort – in other words, presently we face a guarantee of overshoot with no guarantee of return. Yet the goal must remain to return to below 1.5°C as soon as possible – which will be at least several decades. Development objectives become even more urgent in the context of immanent exceedance of 1.5°C.

Critiquing the 1.5°C threshold and advocating for a new, equitable narrative. Some participants highlighted that 1.5°C is a political construct and a focus on thresholds has the potential to back us into a corner. While 1.5°C was initially successful, through a chain of signification, as we get closer to 1.5°C, a focus on 1.5°C as a threshold has contributed to the current political paralysis linked to the oft-repeated “keep 1.5 alive” mantra which is creating a policy-science disconnect. Another way of thinking about this is that overshoot of the threshold fetishizes numbers, whereas there is no sharp turn. Thus, there is a need to find other ways of conveying urgency. One productive approach could be talking about what is fair and equitable in a world beyond 1.5°C of global warming rather than focus on overshoot and return. In this context, participants acknowledged potential benefits in a shift from a rigid 1.5°C-as-a-threshold storyline to a new narrative that does not contribute to the same political paralysis (“is not politically destructive”) and includes a narrative that illustrates how a step-change in action may facilitate a return to 1.5°C.

Accelerating equitable development in a warmer world. Participants thought that a people-centered approach should be taken to overshoot – recognizing that the “pain of transition” will in particular fall on economically marginalized people, their experiences and needs should determine responses. In this context, fairness and equity would require refocusing on measuring success in terms of human well-being and development performance (as opposed to: in terms of a numerical temperature goal). Thus, more productive conversations between the climate and development communities are required to develop more resilient

2 Solar Radiation Management (SRM) was mentioned briefly in the conversation. While most participants viewed SRM as incompatible with equitable adaptation, others suggested that, given the substantial likelihood that some actors will take unilateral action with regards to SRM, its equity implications merit critical examination.

development pathways. There is a need to accelerate the development agenda to enhance robustness of the response to living in a world beyond 1.5°C. There was a shared understanding among participants of the importance of addressing development and climate together. Yet, participants also notes that we currently lack analytical tools to articulate and implement integrated development-climate approaches. Tools that could, among others, help articulate how pursuing sustainable and equitable development would look like in an ever-warming world with an ever-increasing and shifting risk landscape?

Navigating risks, including narrative risks. In a world beyond 1.5°C of global warming, there is a need for a more sophisticated risk management approach to address fairness and equity concerns given the increase in risks, impacts and losses and damages. This also necessitates narrative shifts. One participant suggested four possible and different shifts in narratives on overshoot of 1.5°C: a) overshoot as a disaster; b) overshoot as a justification to full embrace and start geo-engineering; c) overshoot as justification to shift the focus from the 1.5°C goal to 2°C; d) overshoot as a justification to “not bother” anymore with climate action. Another participant suggested that a narrative that “1.5 is dead” would have severe deleterious impacts on the legitimacy of the Paris Agreement. A key challenge is how to convey a message of urgency linked to the idea that every increment of warming matters, and how to productively position such messaging between denial and despair. Most participants shared the view that the narrative should include a call to action.

Adapting to higher warming levels and unpacking long-term implications. Because recent research challenges the idea of the reversibility of overshoot, we need to unpack what higher levels of warming (e.g. a 2°C world) look like from a response position, including, crucially, for adaptation. This conversation should include what it means to adapt to exceeding 1.5°C, 2°C, or 2.5°C – a conversation is needed about what higher levels of warming, with their adaptation challenges and limits, mean for fairness and equity. Also need more information from adaptation community on why every increment of warming matters. There is a closing window for adaptation given the long terms decisions currently being taken around infrastructure and spatial planning which will have implications for fairness and equity. Implications of overshoot include the need for sustainable and sustained levels of CDR (see separate section “Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) and Fair Ambition”).

Developing new capabilities and engaging stakeholders in responses. Living in a world beyond 1.5°C means we need “more of everything” (in terms of responses to adaptation and mitigation) but not “more of the same.” Participants highlighted that there are other capabilities that need to be put in place to respond in a fair and equitable way to an overshoot of 1.5°C, including, crucially, capabilities that have not yet been identified. Thus, there is a need to systematically and compellingly articulate the challenges of living in a world beyond 1.5°C, so people can see themselves in the responses needed to address these challenges. Participants wondered what the best entry point for this discussion could be.

Equity in Climate Finance

Discussions highlighted that unclear definitions and lack of benchmarks hinder applying equity to climate finance. They stressed the need for fair burden-sharing, scaled-up funding, and integration of principles like historical responsibility. Current finance is insufficient, fragmented, and inequitable, requiring major reforms and innovative tools. Equitable, transparent systems centered on local needs and global justice are essential to close gaps, support vulnerable countries, and enable ambitious climate action.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Key considerations for equitable and ambitious climate finance: An international perspective.”

Applying equity principles to the problem space of climate finance faces several persistent challenges. First, there is limited clarity on what the precise meaning of the terms “climate finance,” “finance for climate action” and related terms, nor is there clarity what types of finance should “count” for each of these concepts. For example, discussions on climate finance often begin from a frame of obligations to provide financial resources rather than, for example, a frame of investment. Without shared definitions and operational benchmarks, equity principles remain difficult to apply within the climate finance problem space.

Clear equity-based benchmarks are urgently needed to guide fundamental questions of who pays, who receives, and for what purpose. The difficulties to apply equity principles to the climate finance problem includes the issue of providing equity-based rationale for those who provide climate finance. In this context, there is a need to reinterpret the principle of “common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities,” in the light of different national circumstances. Moral and legal obligations under international law remain underused tools for driving fair and predictable financing, in the current post-colonial context.

Equitable finance is not just about justice but is a pragmatic necessity for ambitious climate action. Developing nations cannot implement meaningful mitigation or adaptation as the necessary scale without fair and sufficient support. Participants were in strong agreement that without scaled-up finance, the ambition of meeting the goals of the Paris Agreement will remain out of reach. Equity principles, including historical responsibility, ecological debt, human rights, intergenerational equity, and intersectional considerations, must be explicitly integrated. Adequate finance also underpins loss and damage responses in vulnerable communities, which remain underfunded despite urgent need.

Fair climate finance delivers benefits to all regions, including high-income nations, by reducing systemic risks and generating net economic advantages globally. Recent modeling shows that fair and ambitious financial mechanisms could halve global economic damages by 2050, compared to current trajectories, and that failure to invest equitably now could result in GDP losses of over 7% by 2050, rising to as much as 40% by 2100.³

Closing the finance gap equitably is urgent and requires pragmatism. There is a large gap between finance provided and mobilized on one hand and what is needed for mitigation and adaptation on the other. Further, needs-based, demand-side, and participatory perspectives are missing from current financing models. Participants cited research that found that finance would have to increase 3 to 6 times to meet

3 Vinca, Adriano; Marina Andrijevic; Edward Byers; Jarmo Kikstra; Setu Pelz; Matthew Gidden; Volker Krey; et al. (2025) "Worldwide Benefits of Fair Climate Finance and Mitigation" In Review. [doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5968289/v1]

mitigation finance needs, and 10 times to meet adaptation finance needs in developing countries. Currently, climate finance amounts to only 1% of global GDP, while achieving Paris-aligned pathways would require raising energy investment alone from 3% to 5% of GDP. These figures underscore both the urgency and scale of the challenge. This is compounded by a one-size-fits-all approach to climate finance flows that does not clearly recognize that the recipients of mitigation and adaptation finance are distinct.

Levels of climate finance provided should be based on clear equity approaches. Crucially, who pays matters as much as how much is paid. Participants highlighted two possible approaches to articulating equity-based response to both questions that operationalize responsibility: a) contributions could be proportional to cumulative CO₂ emissions, and b) a “carbon debt” principle requiring compensation from countries that overshot their fair share of the carbon budget.⁴

Very substantial amounts of public finance can be rapidly mobilized when there is political will. Public finance is often portrayed as scarce, yet recent crises have shown that resources can be mobilized rapidly when there is political will. The distinction between public and private finance is not always meaningful, as both need to be mobilized strategically with equity in mind. Beyond government-to-government transfers, the financial sector, including private banking and development banks (MDBs) could be engaged more deeply with tools such as de-risking, and public guarantees. This could open up substantial progress on financing for climate action, even in a context where public climate finance remains severely constrained. Additionally, the relevance of the Paris Agreement’s Article 2.1.c for adaptation finance specifically is underexplored, and equity should guide how climate resilient development pathways are defined and funded.

Equitable finance must prioritize local needs and capacities, and protection for the vulnerable from market risks. Over-monetization and market-driven approaches have often left vulnerable communities more exposed to private sector risks, rather than shielding them. Current financing mechanisms too often overlook local needs and fail to invest in institutional capacity required to absorb and manage funds. In addition, high transaction costs and bureaucratic hurdles create additional barriers for vulnerable and marginalized communities trying to access climate funds, even for small grants.

Governance of climate finance is fragmented, opaque and inequitable. Current climate finance governance is highly fragmented and burdensome, undermining both accessibility and accountability. Contrary to expectations, financial reporting rules are inconsistently applied, leading to skepticism over whether reported finance figures are accurate, mobilized, or genuinely new and additional. Lack of transparency and accountability for finance means the foundation for assessing equity and effectiveness is weak. Systematic capacity building is needed at all levels to strengthen governance.

Fundamental institutional reform is essential to align international financial architecture with climate justice. Most felt that the existing financial institutions and structures are not fit for purpose to deliver equitable and ambitious climate finance. Participants explored different views, some advocating pragmatic reform within the current system and others emphasizing that more radical restructuring of the financial system would be required to effectively foster climate justice. More specifically, legacy institutions like the World Bank (WB) and International Monetary Fund (IMF) would require fundamental change to enable them to accommodate new ideas effectively. For example, “mission-oriented” architecture could help ensure that funding has a clear connection to its objectives, including equity. It was also pointed out

4 Both illustrated, for example, by: Pelz, Setu; Gaurav Ganti; Robin Lamboll; Luke Grant; Chris Smith; Shonali Pachauri; Joeri Rogelj; et al. (2025) "Using Net-Zero Carbon Debt to Track Climate Overshoot Responsibility" in *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 122(13), e2409316122. [doi: 10.1073/pnas.2409316122]

that, since the recipients of mitigation and adaptation finance are distinct, including in their characteristics and needs, approaches to mitigation and adaptation finance should be different from each other to be responsive to the specific circumstances.

Innovative instruments for climate finance must not repeat the mistakes of development aid. New platforms, such as the Just Energy Transition Partnerships (JETPs), risk reproducing the inequities of structural adjustment programs, if not carefully designed. These risks include loss of national sovereignty and social protections. Some case studies that were discussed, highlighted that JETPs often lack the concrete, fine-grained intermediate steps necessary to effectively link local socio-economic development (the ‘just’ part of transitions) to finance flows. Even where development was supported, the scale of finance was orders of magnitude less than finance for decommissioning fossil fuel infrastructure. Truly equitable design must center local development priorities and ensure that local people are empowered to make decisions about their future.

Equity and Ambition in Global IAMs and Various Applications

Discussions considered Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) as key tools for climate scenarios but emphasized their limitations, especially in addressing equity. Concerns included least-cost optimization, embedded inequalities, and misinterpretation of scenarios as prescriptive. Current models often perpetuate global disparities and overlook social costs. Participants emphasized the need for broader definitions of feasibility, inclusion of equity and finance, improved narratives linking climate and development, and more representative, justice-oriented modeling approaches.

Understanding IAMs. Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) are understood broadly as models producing future projections or modeled scenarios, often with economics at their core. IAMs are used to understand global climate outcomes under certain set of constraints and assumptions, notably global modelled mitigation pathways consistent with 1.5°C and other warming levels. Global modelled mitigation pathways have been extensively assessed in IPCC Working Group III reports on mitigation, though such pathways are highly contested.

Scenario Interpretation – Describing plausible futures vs prescribing requirements. Some participants expressed concern that users’ interpretations of what scenarios represent – especially in the IPCC Summary for Policymakers (SPM) and in COP decisions – shifts from merely describing plausible futures to prescribing what the world “must” or “needs to” do. This tends to obscure underlying assumptions, limitations and inequalities, as headline statements often focus solely on emissions reductions, warming outcomes and similar metrics. Other participants suggested that IAMs should be used to explore a large scenario space by varying assumptions about socioeconomic development pathways.

Like any tool, current IAMs have limits. Participants recognized that IAMs have limitations, like any tool; however there was disagreement about the severity of limitations and the implications. Several participants argued that IAMs tend not to deal well with equity. Other limitations, which are especially relevant for equity considerations, related to the fact that IAMs typically optimize for least-cost, as opposed to for other parameters. Many modelers consider equity is too normative and thus consider it beyond the scope of IAMs. Some participants pointed out that equity has not been explicitly addressed well in IAMs, though implicit normative perspectives are encoded in many of each IAMs assumptions.

Persistent inequality in IAM mitigation pathways in AR6 Scenarios. A critique of IPCC AR6 WGIII scenarios is tendency to model the persistence of present inequalities well into the future. Some participants argued that such scenarios perpetuate or aggravate existing disparities across indicators like GDP, energy consumption, and per capita fossil fuel use. Some argued that the benefits of a higher carbon budget often accrue to developed countries, while developing countries face greater restrictions on energy use and higher burdens of carbon dioxide removal (CDR). The reliance on land use for afforestation and energy crops for CDR can also lead to millions of people remaining at risk of hunger, with none of the modelled scenarios meeting the SDG goal of zero hunger.

Underlying Model Logic – techno-economic optimization sidelines equity-relevant dimensions.

Participants raised concerns about the fundamental techno-economic and global optimisation logic of IAMs, which may overlook country-specific circumstances, objectives, and potentially impose inequitable burdens (e.g., resulting in disproportionately placing the burden of coal phase-out on the Global South). The use of optimisation itself was questioned for its ability to reflect complex political and aspirational drivers of policy.

Redefining “Cost” and “Feasibility.” The discussion highlighted the need to broaden the definition of “cost” beyond mitigation costs to include climate impacts, adaptation costs, and loss and damage, as well as indirect costs of mitigation policies, all of which are often disproportionately borne by the poor and developing countries. There was a strong view that least-cost solutions should not be equated with feasibility, especially when considering social and human costs like the risk of hunger (i.e. a suite of policies that emerges as least-cost in an IAM scenario cannot necessarily be considered feasible if barriers and policy impacts, such as increased risk of hunger, render it infeasible).

Exogenous climate finance assumptions to address equity shortcomings. A long-standing insight from IAM modelling results indicates that substantial international financial transfers (typically not modelled) would be needed to make the distributionary impact of globally cost-optimized mitigation pathways consistent with equity considerations. Some participants argued that a “trilemma of collective mitigation action” highlights the tension between sovereignty,⁵ cost efficiency, and equity/fairness. The IAM community has generally taken the approach to separate questions of cost-efficiency (who undertakes mitigation efforts) from equity (who pays for those mitigation efforts), with the former being a central model output and the latter generally not addressed in IAMs. Regarding the “trilemma,” one participant suggested that one can usually resolve for two out of three dimensions, but not for all of them simultaneously. Other participants took the view that IAMs should address questions of “who pays” more directly, and if results assume large financial transfers from developed to developing countries, they should be clearly reported as integral elements of the overall model results. Another proposition was that equitable distributions of the mitigation burden can (and therefore should) be modelled, and, further, that a future world in which inequalities in income, energy, overall well-being are reduced or eliminated can (and therefore should) be modelled. Both options would provide important insights into the equity dimensions of modelled pathways.

Scenario narratives, especially development narratives, are important. There was broad alignment on the importance of narratives in driving change and influencing policy. The discussion emphasized the need for new stories that link climate action directly to the development agenda, stressing that equity is fundamental to development and that models need to reflect this integration more effectively.

5 Despite other differences in views, participants agreed that “grandfathering” of emissions rights is not an ethical basis for allocation, even though it is sometimes characterized in the literature as a reflection of the “sovereignty” principle.

Efforts to better address equity in IAMs are emerging. Participants from the IAM community reported that they are actively engaging with equity considerations, exploring scenarios that model higher socioeconomic convergence in per capita GDP, energy consumption (particularly final energy and energy services), and dietary changes. This moves beyond the standard Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) framework. It was also noted that the IAM community is actively working to increase representation from Global South scholars to incorporate a broader range of perspectives. In the discussion, participants highlighted that IAMs should specifically model the eradication of poverty as a priority, as it is part of the aim of the Paris Agreement. A specific idea in this regard was to assume a minimum income of \$28,000 per person by 2050. Others mentioned approaches of excluding “survival emissions” from analysis of fair shares.

Can climate action address all inequalities, none or some? The session debated whether climate action should aim to solve all justice issues or only those directly related to climate change. Arguments for integration included positive duties of justice and pragmatic benefits, while limitations included the risk of overloading climate policy and undermining broader support. It was suggested that **all climate policies are inherently integrationist to some degree** given the intimate tie between climate change and development pathways.

Fair Shares and National Emissions Pathways

Participants considered fair shares in the context of national emissions pathways, complementing another discussion on global mitigation pathways. Discussions distinguished normative ‘fair shares’ and modeled national emission pathways, noting tensions between carbon budget sharing and effort-sharing approaches. As the remaining carbon budget shrinks, effort-sharing gains relevance. Grandfathering and least-cost allocation were rejected as inequitable. Results consistently show stricter obligations for developed countries. Bridging gaps between fair shares and pathways may involve finance, with equity closely tied to sustainable development and human rights.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “National Mitigation Pathways and Fair Share Analysis.”

Fair shares and national emissions pathways are different. Fair shares (based on “purely” normative criteria) and “national emissions pathways” (representing “highest possible ambition,” however defined) are connected-but-different matters, with different fundamental approaches of defining them; though both have important ethical and normative dimensions, even if implicit.

Fair shares of a global carbon budget seems clear and simple, but loses relevant with diminishing budget; fair shares of burden or effort offers alternative. Participants exchanged different views, some strongly held, whether fair shares of the mitigation effort or fair shares of a global carbon budget are the more appropriate way of defining “fair shares.” Sharing of carbon budget can be an attractive method because of its simplicity. However, there are different allocation principles, including responsibility, capability, the right to promote sustainable development and more. There are different global carbon budgets (GCBs), yet some felt this becomes irrelevant as we get closer to a very small, or exhausted, remaining GCB, thus leading nothing to share equitably. Others pointed out that upward of four-fifths of the total GCB for 1.5°C have been spent historically and that this is the reason that so little is left. Other participants argued for fair sharing of efforts, but this has also its limitations, e.g., chiefly, its dependence on a baseline scenario and a particular mitigation scenario to define the effort.

Normative relevance of emissions differs with underlying activity. Differences in the normative relevance of different emissions were highlighted on the basis of: the nature of the underlying activity and their importance for human welfare (e.g. subsistence vs luxury emissions); the timing of the emissions (past, future – including the consideration of leaving “carbon space” for future generations, especially in countries unable to utilize it now or in the past); and others.

Grandfathering and least-cost are indefensible as equitable allocation principles, excluding them narrows the range of fair shares. Participants shared the view that allocating emissions due to high past or current emissions (“grandfathering”) is not ethically defensible. Least-cost as a principle is not consistent with international environmental law, and similarly should be excluded as an allocation principle. Allocation of a budget is distinct from least-cost as an analytical tool, as was clarified in discussion (many models optimize for least-cost, but do not necessarily assume that the costs have to be borne by the same entity undertaking the action – see section “Equity and Ambition in Global IAMs and Various Applications” above). Further narrowing of fair share ranges might be considered, to find ways of agreeing on basic criteria for defensible allocation principles fair shares. If a country’s emission pathway falls outside the full range of fair shares, that would be compelling finding. Benchmarks or benchmark ranges are useful for certain applications, including court cases.

Despite large variation, results feature important common features. Despite often large range of results from different studies (or even within the same study), results of defensible fair shares analyses share common features. For example, developed countries’ fair shares are much more stringent than “feasible” domestic pathways in these countries. Other participants suggested that considering not only domestic mitigation, but also finance for mitigation elsewhere can address negative fair shares allocations for a country.

Should finance fill the gap between fair shares and national emission pathways? The gap between fair shares and “national emissions pathways” is important, often sizable. The gap can be used to inform questions on the scale of climate finance, and other forms of cooperations. Some participants were of the view that this must not replace the legal obligation of providing climate finance, others holding that there might be ways of monetizing this gap. Most participants shared the view that internationally transferred mitigation outcomes (ITMOs) are not a suitable way of closing (or monetizing) the gap.

The link to sustainable development is central and crucial. While discussions centered on emissions, using the language of the international climate regime, participants also highlighted that emissions are often a proxy for equitable access to sustainable development and the human right to a dignified life. There were different views whether this link between a right to development and emissions resulted in a right to emissions space.

Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) and Fair Ambition

Participants emphasized that carbon dioxide removal (CDR) is essential for achieving net zero, compensating residual emissions, and enabling temperature reductions after overshoot. However, its future scale, effectiveness, and permanence remain uncertain, with significant equity and sustainability concerns. Land-based CDR creates trade-offs with food security and development. Fair allocation of responsibility, stronger governance, and careful integration with emissions reductions are critical for equitable and effective deployment.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) and equity.”

Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) methods are integral to ambition and equity. Achieving global net zero emissions by 2050 will depend on CDR, especially for residual GHG emissions that have not been reduced. Some CDR methods have distributional implications and may therefore undermined other sustainable development goals. CDR is important in scenarios, narratives and modeling of fair ambition.

Two roles of CDR – or even three? The IPCC refers to two roles of CDR in scenarios of net zero emissions, compensating residual emissions from hard-to-abate activities, and achieving net-negative emissions to help return to lower temperatures after a temperature overshoot. A third, related, role for the use of CDR is to achieve net zero emissions earlier than exclusive reliance on emissions reduction would enable, thus reducing cumulative emissions and thereby peak temperatures. These roles are important for ambitious global mitigation.

The scale of CDR has historically been small, and future projections vary depending on scenario design. CDR has in recent history been small, less than half of what governments pledge, and a quarter of estimated economic potential of CDR in 2050. The scale of carbon dioxide removed from the atmosphere in the land sector over the past decade is $1.8 \text{ GtCO}_2\text{y}^{-1}$ in scenarios, though with 7 GtCO_2 of deforestation emissions, land remains a net source of 5 GtCO_2 annually. Countries’ current pledges include CDR of 5 GtCO_2 per year; the majority in conventional removal approaches, mostly in the land sector. Estimates of future CDR are a technical potential of 28.4 GtCO_2 in 2050 (based on sectoral analysis), with economic potential – at a modeled carbon price – is 7.9 GtCO_2 in 2050. (see discussion paper “Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) and equity” in the appendix)

Future use of CDR varies based on scenario design. Modeled scenarios with high ambition in emission reductions reduce emissions by 80% relative to baseline and the remaining 20% to achieve net-zero is achieved through removals. On the other hand, scenarios that assume less ambitious emissions reductions have much larger scale of CDR. In scenario results, reporting net negative emissions instead of gross sequestration can obscure the scale of the sequestration required and thus of the associated policy challenges for deployment and the scale of any deleterious impacts.

High uncertainty whether new CDR methods can actually deliver permanent removals. In reality, removals must be permanently stored away from the atmosphere for CDR to counterbalance or remove emissions from fossil fuels (“geological net zero”). Yet the majority of current, pledged and modelled CDR is based on enhancing terrestrial sinks or on carbon neutrality assumptions for bioenergy. Also, most new CDR methods are at early stages of development of technology and processes, with substantial remaining concerns regarding the possibility of deployment at scale, which increases the uncertainty regarding future

success or failure. The most “mature” CDR methods related to afforestation. However, the impermanence of biospheric storage limits utility of afforestation for CDR compared to land-use trade-offs.

Land-based CDR competes with other land uses, and there are tensions with other sustainable development objectives. The extensive use of land-based CDR methods has significant trade-offs with other sustainable development objectives. Competition with other land uses affects agriculture, and threatens food security (inconsistent with the Paris Agreement’s Article 2.1.b). These and other risks of deploying CDR at scale need to be carefully managed. The discussion considered the question whether it is possible to identify development co-benefits of CDR in addition to potential negative impacts? For example, ecosystem restoration should be pursued for non-climate, developmental benefits.

Who is responsible for deploying CDR, paying for it, and with what consequences? The opportunity and obligation to undertake CDR are not equally distributed amongst actors and geographies. Studies that utilize a fair shares approach to distribute the burden to implement CDR between nations, using responsibility and capacity, find CDR responsibilities 2-3 times larger for the US, EU and China compared with a global least-cost approaches.

Equity in CDR – a sustainable budget or carbon take-back obligation? One potential proposal for implementing an equitable approach to CDR deployment is to estimate a sustainable CDR budget based on socio-ecological thresholds, which would then require allocating limited CDR supply where it has the greatest benefit to human welfare. Another proposal could be to conceptualize and calculate a carbon takeback obligation for fossil fuel producers, based on the polluter pays principle. Yet others suggest treating CDR as a public good, akin to waste management.

Strong governance will be needed for CDR. Governance challenges include issues of who pays, whether using economic instruments, such as carbon pricing, or regulatory approaches, such as public funds spent for the public good. Other ideas included separate targets, to regulate balance between emission reductions and removals in reaching net-zero emissions.

Equity in Distributing the Benefits of Decarbonization

Participants explored reframing decarbonisation as an opportunity rather than a burden, emphasizing economic gains, industrial policy, and clean energy value creation. Participants discussed how these gains are currently distributed, the limitations of existing analytical tools and policy frameworks in addressing this, and the broader geopolitical context shaping these dynamics. In a turbulent geopolitical context, major economies are focussing on domestically capturing the benefits of decarbonization, instead of considering their equitable distribution. A justice-based approach – addressing both benefits and risks – was highlighted as essential.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Equity and fairness in the distribution of gains from decarbonization.”

Can we re-frame decarbonisation as an opportunity and emphasize gains? Reframing would highlight the significant economic opportunities and “gains” that could be achieved through decarbonization. Such gains may arise from decarbonisation itself, and may also indirectly arise as a result of broadening the focus to domains such as industrial policy and even the pursuit of economic dominance or, conversely, economic independency.

Current analysis tends to focus on costs and burdens. Existing models and policy frameworks are primarily “skewed toward costs” and therefore, where they consider equity in mitigation, they tend to frame it as relating to equitable distribution of burden or effort. Such analysis lacks the necessary granularity and integrated analysis to adequately assess and suggest equitable distribution of diverse benefits and economic rents generated by decarbonisation. This gap means that important questions are often not fully explored; for example, questions about who gains, how much, and how value is distributed in the clean energy value chain. Reframing the conversation around gains and opportunities is potentially more helpful – yet there are challenges to this approach too.

Highly uncertain geopolitical landscape. Participants reflected on turbulent and highly uncertain geopolitics and geo-economics. The importance of climate change as a policy priority is undermined outright in some salient narratives, and where motivations for climate action continue, they seem increasingly driven by the pursuit of global economic power and dominance. This context fosters unilateral actions and approaches, potentially eroding established international “rules of the game.”

Will countries seek to capture benefits nationalistically? Participants reflected on how major economies, including the US, EU, and China, are actively pursuing policies (e.g., the US Inflation Reduction Act, the EU Green Deal) with the explicit intent of domestically capturing economic benefits of mitigation policies, such as job creation and leadership in clean technology manufacturing. Several participants felt that such approaches, however, often overlook potential negative spillovers on developing countries.

Resource nationalism in critical mineral value chains. While developed countries focus on securing critical mineral supply chains for their own consumption, there is limited work on how resource-rich but energy-poor developing countries, such as the Democratic Republic of Congo, can equitably and sustainably leverage these resources to improve energy access of their own populations and drive their own economic growth. Participants noted that China plays a very significant role in several of the value chains that have relevance for decarbonization efforts, and this is contested. “When elephants fight, the grass gets trampled.”

Need for a justice frame for benefits of decarbonisation. Participants arrived at a shared understanding that it is important to apply a “justice frame” when considering the distribution of gains and losses, encompassing both distributive and procedural justice. The importance of developing positive and compelling narratives that link climate action directly to development opportunities and address equity concerns was highlighted as crucial for driving change and overcoming resistance. However, it was also cautioned that “co-benefits” can come with “co-costs” that need to be considered.

Climate Policy and Distributive Justice: Philosophical Perspectives on Equity

Participants explored whether climate action address can and should address all/some/none of other equity and socio-economic inequalities, and what complementary developmental policies are needed to achieve equitable outcomes? Perspectives from philosophy were presented, focussing on the concept of integrationist and isolationist views. While integration can build support and reflect real-world linkages, it has limits: overloading policies or misaligning objectives may backfire. Ultimately, an integrationist approach – sensitive to trade-offs and development needs – was seen as essential for effective and equitable climate action.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Climate Justice and its Relationship to Other Issues of Justice.”

Utilitarian, rights-based, and egalitarian ethics support integrating justice goals into climate

action. Climate policy should address other, non-climate, justice issues for three reasons: 1) there are positive duties of justice according to multiple plausible moral theories (utilitarianism, rights-based views, egalitarianism), which would at minimum support choosing a climate policy that advanced other justice objectives over one that did not; 2) linking multiple justice issues may have pragmatic benefits by drawing support of broader constituencies, 3) most “climate” policies are not strictly speaking only about climate and can be framed in other terms (and therefore may appropriately address justice in those other domains). Policies (like carbon taxes or renewable subsidies) address multiple issues simultaneously (e.g., climate, air pollution, employment, energy security) and are appropriately designed for multiple objectives. If Policy A and Policy B are equally good at mitigating climate change, but A also addresses another issue (poverty, malnutrition), A should be preferred (co-benefits).

Isolationism in climate policy is untenable due to interconnected justice challenges. A fully isolationist position (treating climate change exclusively) seems implausible because climate policies profoundly affect livelihoods, health, and development. Rather, all climate policies are integrationist to some degree. Climate change is intimately tied to development pathways; thus, isolationism is implausible. This means that new initiatives will not succeed without development being central.

However, there are three key limitations to integrationist approaches: 1) Climate policy may not be the best way to address all injustices, some of which should be addressed squarely on their own terms. 2) Overloading too many justice issues onto climate policy can be problematic/unwieldy. Climate policy may not be the best way to address deep injustices (e.g., unfair terms of trade, odious debt), which require tackling root causes. 3) Some linkages to other issue areas may actually undermine broader support and achievability of a reaching climate goals. Linking climate with other goals is not *always* practically possible; some stakeholders will only endorse climate policies if they are *not* linked to certain other issues.

Potential for integration with other policy objectives differ for adaptation and mitigation. The integration of adaptation with development is inherent, because it is necessarily already integrated. Mitigation faces steeper integration challenges because it is often approached from burden perspective rather than opportunity perspective. Additionally, separate adaptation funding for vulnerability (development funding) and impacts (adaptation funding) limits integration. An integrationist approach is favoured when considering that policymakers have a negative duty not to impose unjust costs and harms (e.g., undermine rights to land, water, food, health, and development). In other words, when designing climate policies, they must ensure that other injustices are not exacerbated. One participant described a possible integrationist view for loss and damage: while the isolationist view would seek to replace the original shelter after climate loss, even if it was inadequate; whereas integrationism would support providing adequate shelter. Instead. The argument from political viability suggests that mitigation policies are unlikely to be supported on purely climate grounds but succeed when linked with other issues such as jobs, clean air, and energy security.

Narratives of Equity and Their Role in Processes

Participants explored how underlying metanarratives shape climate and development discourse, influencing views on justice, power, and solutions. Despite differing perspectives, participants' differing narratives emphasized shared elements of justice, equity and wellbeing. Discussions highlighted gaps between reality and ideals, and stressed aligning narratives with audiences, listening carefully, and leveraging messengers; framing climate action in both challenges and solutions can be effective depending on the specific situation.

Note: This session was informed by a discussion paper prepared by a participant and annexed to these proceedings as “Wielding the Narrative Knife: Open Questions for Climate Equity Analysts.”

Metanarratives shape explicit narratives of climate and development including equity dimensions.

Participants reflected on their own metanarratives and how their own metanarratives may be shaping the explicit narratives they then use for understanding the climate and development challenges (and their equity dimensions) and in communicating their understanding of these challenges to others. Reflections on metanarratives focussed on the questions: 1) What are the foundational hopes and fears in the climate and development space? 2) How people think the world DOES work? 3) How people think the world SHOULD work / what moral framings would be ideal? 4) What do people think is the core challenge, and what, ultimately, causes is? (and by extension, where may solutions lie?)

Despite different preferences in metanarrative and narratives, substantial overlaps concern centrality of justice and equity.

In discussing the question “Right now, in this political moment, what narratives do we need?,” participants recognized that despite different participants preferring different external narratives or holding different positions on various issues, there was a lot of overlap in terms of specific elements of their narratives and metanarratives. This overlap included experiences of the underlying sets of fears and overlap regarding ideas about how the world works (e.g., various forms of power were mentioned repeatedly). Additionally, there was substantial overlap regarding an overarching desire for greater equality and human flourishing and wellbeing.

There is a gap between how we think the world is working and how we would like it to be. An open question that emerged several times was whether this group was operating in a bubble, with a focus on the world as we would like it to be. However, we also considered that others outside the climate bubble have similar concerns.

It is unclear whether it is preferable to shape the narrative to the objective, to the audience, or to the messenger. Discussions emphasized shaping underlying narratives, as well as developing narratives that can make a difference. Some challenged the idea that the focus should be on the question of “what narratives to put out” (to effectively shape discourse). Instead, they encouraged to focus more on “how to listen” so that the work corresponds more closely to the meta-narratives that audiences are already using. Others suggested this was also a concrete focus, connecting with priorities and beliefs. Yet others made the point that narratives matter but so too do narrators: who carries what message is extremely important.

Narratives can be framed around successes or failures. One narrative example used the concept of “market failure” explicitly, whereas, instead, a narrative emphasizing problem-solving might be framed around ingenuity and innovation. Political narratives often point to obstacles and barriers, whereas other narratives can tell stories of overcoming challenges.

Climate Litigation and the ICJ Advisory Opinion

Participants explored how the use of the equity arguments – in particular around “fair shares” – are used in climate litigation, especially in the light of the landmark Advisory Opinion of the International Court of Justice. Participants discussed how growing climate litigation based on “fair shares” strengthens legal obligations, despite courts focusing on minimum standards. Challenges include shifting benchmarks, scientific uncertainty, and unclear links to negotiations, while climate finance remains a central yet unresolved issue.

The ICJ opinion confirms 1.5°C as the operational temperature goal. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) issued an Advisory Opinion (AO) on the obligations of states in relation to climate change, which confirms 1.5°C to be “the parties’ agreed primary temperature goal” under the Paris Agreement.⁶ (For a further discussion on the ICJ’s interpretation of the 1.5°C goal and the resulting limits to state discretion, see section “International Environment Law Principles and Quantified Fair Shares” below)

The AO strongly emphasizes the duty to cooperate. The discussions noted the ICJ’s call for states to determine their “fair shares” via transparent methodologies. This effectively could translate normative principles into concrete legal requirements for subsequent litigation. However, the AO stops short of specifying a methodology or identify specific indicators of equity (it leaves this discretion to the states).

Growing body of climate litigation strengthens legal case for “fair share” obligation. Increasing numbers of lawsuits have been initiated by citizens against states (on mitigation, adaptation and reparation) and against corporations. Landmark cases like Urgenda, Neubauer, and the ECHR Klimaseniorinnen case established an obligation for states to contribute their “fair share” towards the 1.5°C goal.

Courts examine breach of “minimum” standards not determination of “right” levels. Courts generally do not prescribe the “right” mitigation targets, but rather determine whether a minimum level of effort that is consistent with applicable legal standards has been met. Participants highlighted that the Paris Agreement has obligations of conduct, not result. However, questions were raised about whether this limitation, was due to concerns regarding human rights violations (if the problem continues) or issues of political acceptability.

The relationship between courts (national, supranational) and multilateral negotiations is unclear. The question was raised regarding the possibility of national courts to adopt coordinated or consistent standards globally when determining a state’s minimum contribution. It was suggested that consistency may increase at higher judicial levels, such as the ICJ and the European Court of Human Rights. Some participants saw national litigation as occurring in a domain separate from the multilateral process, while others disagreed, arguing that it happens because multi-lateral negotiations are not working fast enough.

Passage of time problematically shifts goal posts for ambition. A critical challenge in litigation is the issue of “shifting goal posts.” Courts look at the latest science, and thus the base year or the starting year for emissions calculations tends to get later, which ignores past failures to comply with legal or moral obligations. To address this, some researchers have decided to calculate the “post-Paris shortfall” between actual emissions and the fair share trajectory the country should have taken since, for example, signing the

6 International Court of Justice (2025) *Obligations of States in Respect of Climate Change*. International Court of Justice. Advisory Opinion. [<https://icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/187/187-20250723-adv-01-00-en.pdf>]

PA, and add this shortfall to future fair share obligations.⁷ While this aims to establish the minimum, the difference it creates between legal results and political feasibility is already very substantial.

Scientific evidence, including fair shares assessments, critical to court cases. Scientific evidence is critical to inform key components of legal claims: foreseeability, breach of duty, causation, harm, and remedy. Establishing harm can be demonstrated by studies attributing the responsibility for climate impacts to substantiate claims that harm has occurred or will occur. Modelling studies linking emissions to temperature rise and probabilistic studies attributing extreme weather events to climate change are important in establishing causation and attribution, and whether emitter can reasonably have been expected to foresee the consequences of their emissions. Claims of breach of duty and arguments for remedies need to be supported by different fair share assessments.

While there are several sources of scientific evidence, the IPCC's assessment are negotiated and often referenced. Sources used for fair share calculations in litigation vary, including IPCC reports, national scientific advisory bodies, peer-reviewed literature, and expert reports. The ICJ AO draws extensively on the IPCC as the “best available science,” acknowledging that the Summaries for Policymakers (SPM) are negotiated and contested, what is approved by governments following line by line review in IPCC plenaries can be taken as scientific consensus. On fair shares, earlier IPCC cycles provided quantitative summary of fair-share allocations, but that stopped after AR5 – more such assessments are needed.

Features of scientific debate (disagreement, iterative process) can be a weakness in court cases. Defendants in court cases can potentially misuse of “academic debate” or disagreement among authors in “fair share” literature to argue that no consensus or minimum standard exists, thereby setting aside the utility of science to inform legal obligations. Moreover, the iterative updates of pathways complicate findings of breach due to “shifting goal posts.” Precaution is an integral principle, requiring science to be taken into account. The ICJ approach suggests caution when technology, such as extreme Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) or Solar Radiation Management (SRM), poses risks.

Climate finance is important in settling legal claims. The legal conditions for providing and mobilising climate finance remain complex, yet settling legal claims would require finance. Some participants pointed to confusion caused by reference to Article 6 credits, as a form of support. Many expressed a strong view that Article 6 is not the same thing as climate finance. Article 6 is seen as an optional tool to meet mitigation obligations, and the use of markets it to reduce costs. However, at best, market mechanisms like Article 6 prevent an increase in GHG emissions.

⁷ E.g., Holz, Ceecee (2024) *Canada's Fair Share of 1.5 °C-Consistent Global Mitigation Through 2035*. Climate Equity Reference Project Working Paper Series. [doi: 10.5281/zenodo.2595506]

International Environment Law Principles and Quantified Fair Shares

Participants discussed how international environmental law principles – such as sustainable development, special circumstances, common but differentiated responsibilities and equity, harm prevention, good faith, cooperation, and the precautionary approach – apply to climate change, emphasizing their evolving interpretation. The International Court of Justice reaffirmed states’ duties to prevent harm and cooperate toward the 1.5 °C goal, thus limiting state discretion. Participants discussed the applicability of quantified fair share methodologies to litigation and considered shifting geopolitical norms shaping interpretation, implementation, and applicability of international environmental law principles.

Principles of international environmental law (IEL) are well established and applicable to climate change. Many principles of IEL were first articulated in the Rio Declaration that emerged from the Earth Summit (1992), including sustainable development, special circumstances, common but differentiated responsibilities and equity (within and between generations), harm prevention, good faith, cooperation, and the precautionary approach. These principles have differing legal status and their core content is subject to an interpretative range. Some IEL principles such as harm prevention and the duty to cooperate are binding as these form part of customary international law, others such as common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities (CBDR&RC) are not binding, but they nevertheless have significant operational salience as they form part of the conceptual architecture of a treaty regime, as for instance in the UN climate regime. Operationalization of principles can change over time. For example, CBDR&RC is operational in a very different way in the Kyoto Protocol compared its application under the Paris Agreement.

ICJ affirms states’ duty to prevent environmental harm and duty to cooperate to prevent such harm. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) in its 2025 Advisory Opinion elaborated at some length on the application of two of these principles – the duty to prevent environmental harm and the duty to cooperate to prevent environmental harm – to climate change. The ICJ identified several applicable principles, including CBDR&RC, which it interpreted as dynamic. By contrast, it found that the polluter pays principle is not applicable to climate change. While major emitting countries had argued that the principle of harm prevention should be limited to cross-boundary harms, the ICJ found harm prevention applies to the global commons. The ICJ AO establishes strict and demanding standards of due diligence in relation to harm prevention.

The ICJ ruling means that 1.5 °C is now the primary agreed temperature goal for Parties. The duty to cooperate is intrinsically linked to the harm prevention principle, and is specifically related to the duty to cooperate to achieve the collective temperature goal. Even further, the AO says that a methodology is needed to determine concrete emission reduction targets for countries that contribute to the global temperature goal in a way that is consistent with the other applicable legal principles.

There are limits to discretion that states have – collectively the NDCs must achieve 1.5 °C. In other words, national determination of effort is limited by the collective obligation to meet the global temperature goal.

Entering 1.5 °C overshoot does not change the PA temperature goal or the Convention’s objective. Participants raised that overshoot of 1.5 °C will happen in a few years. However, it was also discussed that does not mean the Paris Agreement’s temperature goal changes, and the goal should be distinguished from actual global warming levels. There was a shared understanding that what mattered was the extent and duration of overshoot. Some raised the importance of increasing ambition, for both support and action, in this context. The relevance of the objective of the Convention – avoiding dangerous interference with the

climate system – was also highlighted in discussion. (see also section “Equity under Condition of “Overshoot”” above)

The ICJ advisory opinion draws extensively on IPCC as “best available science.” This was informed by the understanding that Summaries for Policymakers are negotiated, and can be taken as consensus on science, albeit negotiated and contested. Some participants expressed reservations about considering the IPCC as the only scientific authority for litigation.

For use in litigation, fair shares studies should exclude results non consistent with IEL. A specific paper was discussed (including its methodologies, strengths and limitations) that investigates the quantification of fair shares in the context of applying IEL principles. It was argued that considering all approaches to quantify fair shares has the benefit of inclusivity. However, the literature includes approaches that are based on principles that not consistent with IEL, thus such approaches should be excluded. For example, studies should exclude grandfathering, global least-cost, and mitigation potential. In the paper that was discussed excluding such approaches showed that the resulting ranges change only to a limited extent. When turning to application, some studies share a carbon budget, while others share effort. The former effectively allocates allowable emissions, whereas the latter share the burden of emission reductions, relative to those required. Grandfathering might not be entirely avoided – unless there is a discontinuous allocation, a sudden “jump” in emission allocations – though some participants questioned if it is appropriate to label allocations as having “grandfathering bias” if they don’t actually allocate based on grandfathering logic. Many participants felt that quantified fair shares, when carefully and ethically assessed, were useful benchmarks.

Participants reflected on the role of IEL and quantified fair shares, in geopolitics. Recently, clear shifts were observed away from rules and towards exercise of hard power for naked self-interest. One response was that the strengthening IEL was a long-term undertaking. Others raised that good faith could not be taken for granted. Good faith is a binding principle of customary law. Whether it can be assumed politically is distinct. The discussion turned again to the duty to cooperate – in good faith – to prevent harm.

Moral and Political Philosophy

Participants explored how moral philosophy helps clarify and evaluate principles for allocating responsibility for climate action, including by examining the concepts of fault for harm caused, beneficiary pays, and ability to pay, highlighting limits of fault-based approaches and debates over fairness in burden-sharing. Participants critiqued grandfathering and equal per capita models, emphasizing equity, sustainable development, and capability-based approaches. Overall, philosophy supports identifying just frameworks to guide mitigation, adaptation, and responsibility in addressing climate change.

Moral philosophy offers important insights for the consideration of equity and ambition in climate.

Participants explored how moral and political philosophy can provide contributions through the clarification and formation of concepts, assessing the implication and application of principles, and defending and criticizing principles. Philosophical inquiry concerns the best principles of justice (doctrine of moral creditors) or responsibility (doctrine of moral debtors) for climate change and in the context of policies in response to climate change. Most of the discussion focused on the application of principles, while noting that there is another school of thought to first identify principles. Discussions covered ethical principles relevant to responsibility for mitigation, such as the Polluter Pays Principle, Fault, No-Fault, Beneficiary Pays, and Ability to Pay.

Responsibility based on fault requires knowledge of harm caused. Since emitters in the distant past will not satisfy this condition, a fault account of responsibility would seem to be limited to the emissions of those people currently living. Many noted that a fault approach leaves responsibility for earlier emissions unassigned.

A Beneficiary Pays principle assigns responsibility to those who have benefited from the actions of others. While this sometimes seems appropriate (e.g. as in receipt of stolen goods), it is not as a general rule appropriate, as when a person's property holds its value due to the good house maintenance of neighbor. The difference seems to be whether the benefit was due to a prior injustice.

Ability to Pay (ATP) is forward-looking principle that dictates that agents should pay in proportion to their capacity to support the creation or maintenance of the good, arrangement, institution, etc. One issue is what counts as the relevant ability and why. A key question arising was how having greater ability incurs an obligation to act. We reflected on parallels between responsibility for emissions and concepts of privilege (e.g., race and gender spaces). It was noted that responsibility and guilt are separate issues, and that responsibility comes from the privilege.

Moral philosophy can guide which principles to apply (or not to apply) to effort sharing problems. Discussions focused on some specific principles, often used to derive allocation mechanisms, or fair shares⁸. Grandfathering (GF) takes a fact (unequal emissions) and turns it into an entitlement. While philosophers might be able to identify defences of GF, such as arguing that a state has developed a reasonable expectation that will continue, most participants viewed this as unethical. They also point to GF not having a basis in international environmental law (see section "International Environment Law Principles and Quantified Fair Shares"). Critics argue that if present emissions levels are unjust or merely arbitrary, GF rewards that; and this institutionalizes and perpetuates an injustice of an arbitrary inequality.

Equal per capita can be seen as isolationist or integrationalist. From the perspective of philosophy, a critique of equal per capita (EPC) approaches was that it applies an entitlement based only on population. A philosophical perspective offered was that EPC tends to be isolationist, isolating emissions from other salient factors, such as resource endowments, income, etc. (see section "Climate Policy and Distributive Justice: Philosophical Perspectives on Equity") Other participants suggested that EPC can be linked to argument for energy access, and the right to promote sustainable development, and thus did not see EPC as isolationist.

Sustainable development is a widely supported equity principle. The right to promote sustainable development is a principle of the UNFCCC, Article 3.4, and is widely supported. This right relates to rights of states (as opposed to individuals) – as it was pointed out that the term "promote" places the right, and agency related to exercising it, in the hands of the state – and creates a claim for international justice. As a principle of international justice, the right to promote sustainable development fits well with an ability to pay principle that takes ability to be measured in human development terms.

The concept of prioritarianism offers important insights for justice concerns in adaptation and capabilities. The concept of prioritarianism in philosophy states that the aim of justice is to improve the lives of worst-off. If the likelihood of being able to respond to all needs is low, the question is how to prioritize. Some participants suggested that equity in adaptation often is reduced to finance, and should also include a relational ethics. Adaptation in implementation is primarily about foundational capabilities, and

⁸ See sections "Fair Shares and National Emissions Pathways" and "International Environment Law Principles and Quantified Fair Shares" as well as the discussion paper "National Mitigation Pathways and Fair Share Analysis."

many saw potential in a capabilities-based approach to equity in adaptation (also see section “Equity under Condition of “Overshoot”” and the discussion paper “Justice Within Limits: Climate Futures and Adaptive Capacity” in the appendix).

Narrative Writing Workshop

Participants examined how dominant narratives shape and obstruct equitable climate policy, focusing on how they function as persuasive stories and political tools. The widely used claim that “fast decarbonization is anti-poor” was identified as widespread and influential despite weak evidence. Discussions emphasized analyzing underlying values and meta-narratives, and using storytelling strategically to challenge misleading claims and better support equitable climate action.

Scholars of equity in climate action should interrogate ways in which to engage with impactful blocking narratives. A virtual Narrative Writing Workshop continued the exploration of narratives and meta-narratives (see section “Narratives of Equity and Their Role in Processes”). This had framed a broader notion of narrative, viewing them as undercurrents of thinking from which specific analysis, evidence, or further stories emerged. In the virtual workshop, participants explored how scholars committed to more equitable climate policy should engage with narratives that generate repeated and fundamental blockages to efforts to advance equitable climate policy. Three questions guided the discussion:

- How narratives that generated these blockages worked internally as stories and externally as political tools.
- How engaging with the underlying components of these narratives might change how participants engaged with analytical frames and tools, evidence, particular people and interest groups, or broader policy processes.
- How narrative or storytelling could or should be used in participants’ own work in light of these reflections.

A problematic “fast decarbonization is anti-poor” narrative is powerfully and frequently deployed despite lack of evidence; its deployment requires further investigation. To make the workshop concrete, we discussed a particular narrative, the notion that “fast decarbonization is anti-poor.” In a poll prior to the workshop, this phrase emerged as the one that participants were most interested in investigating further. This narrative had been identified as generating a repeated and fundamental blockage to efforts to advance equitable climate policy. Many participants shared that “fast decarbonization is anti-poor” is a narrative that they encounter in their own specific contexts. Some participants found the narrative very powerful for delaying climate action. Others observed that actors promoting the narrative typically present very little evidence – the telling of the narrative assume it is true. Participants observed that this seems to be because the narrative “holds together” as a story, despite being disconnected from evidence. The narrative also connects to other salient narratives, which are taken as given in various countries and communities. Deeper exploration is needed on how this narrative gets mobilized.

Participants discussed the undercurrents of thinking and underlying values and interests. Meta-narratives reflect foundational hopes and fears in the climate and development space. The distinction between how the work does work and how it should work was recalled (see section “Narratives of Equity and Their Role in Processes”). We also engaged in a practical writing exercise, writing stories that would engage with and counter such narratives.

How Scenarios Are Used

Participants discussed multiple dimensions of success for modelled climate scenarios: effectively simplifying complexity without distortion, balancing ambition and equity, enabling actionable insights, and supporting policy through comparison of diverse scenarios. Scenarios were also seen as tools to expand imagination and agency. However, gaps persist between modelers and policymakers, including misinterpretations, unclear definitions, and misuse of global results. Greater transparency, attention to equity, and active engagement between scenario developers and users were emphasized to ensure responsible application in climate policy.

How do modelled scenarios get used successfully?

Success as accurately translating complexity into simple messages. Some participants suggested that scenarios are considered successful if they manage to translate complexity into simple messages, while retaining accuracy. Examples of the UNEP emission gap report as a high-quality result of modeling, translated into something clear and impactful. Other examples were cited too. Proponents of this interpretation noted that one should guard against overreliance, particularly that the success of simple messages might lead to a false sense of feasibility. Other participants saw the way in which such scenarios influenced the IPCC, and then were socialized into other processes, as problematic.

Success as comprehensively balancing important values and considerations. Some participants indicated that scenarios would be considered successes if they balanced and incorporated the most important values, considerations and dimensions, i.e. included both ambition and equity, were based in science, incorporated development and climate dynamics, and covered the full breadth of mitigation, adaptation, loss and damage, and means of implementation (finance, technology, capacity).

Success as being actionable. Some participants wondered to what degree scenarios can be made actionable? This question built on the previous assertion that a comprehensive balance of important dimensions constitutes success, suggesting that scenarios are successful if they are useful for implementation and account for technical and social dimensions, including equity.

Success requires structured comparison of multiple scenarios. Structured comparison of multiple scenarios is key for scenario use in policy development, rather than any one scenario or median result. It was suggested that the primary value lies in comparing multiple scenarios to link interventions to outcomes and derive actionable insights. A related point raised was that large ensembles of models can provide more robust insights. Yet sometimes results from ensembles get reduced to single numbers or averages, especially when translated into policy discussions. In this context, a plurality of scenarios and models are helpful. Also, a bottom-up approach was suggested, beginning with national modelling (access, fuels, development, equity) rather than downscaling global SSPs.

Success as expanding imagination and promoting agency. A participant asked how to ensure scenarios expand, rather than constrain, our imaginations and sense of agency. Others supported this approach, referring to scenarios as “stories told in words and numbers, with rigour and imagination.” Thus, modelled scenarios might be informed by narrative storylines, and model results support certain narratives. In terms of process, co-design of scenarios between modelers and decision-makers can be helpful to facilitate both rigour and imagination.

What are the gaps between how modelers think about scenarios and how policymakers interpret or use them?

Are scenarios conversation starters or prescriptive outcomes? A participant provided a kick-off input, outlining several misperceptions of modeled scenarios: i) Available scenarios cover all futures – they do not; ii) all modelled scenarios are desirable – they are not; iii) if a scenario exists, it is possible – not necessarily; iv) imperfections make scenarios useless – they do not. Participants discussed these misperceptions and debated critiques of models and their use.

Scenarios do not cover all possible futures. Participants shared the view that scenarios do not cover all possible futures, for various reasons. Modelled scenarios seek to investigate particular policy questions, including equity approaches. Another reason is that many models do not include equity considerations well. The discussion also turned to possible alternatives to modelled scenarios, with some suggesting that inclusivity and visioning mattered.

Different uses of the term “scenario” leads to misunderstanding. Participants noticed that “scenario” was being used with different meaning. Using the same word when meaning different things results in misunderstanding. In this discussion, many assumed scenarios to referring to modeling. Others highlighted that scenarios comprise quantitative and qualitative elements; and are provided by making models and narratives. Even then, some participants consider modeling to include both: Scenarios include narratives (qualitative), quantified outcomes, and models (analytical tools). Another participant suggested working definitions – i) Narrative: painting with words the society we envision in future; ii) Pathways: Trajectory from present to future, or future to present, typically modeled, emphasis is on numbers; iii) Storylines: can mean a) the narratives, or the story, or b) description of modeled pathways in words, then translated into numbers; iv) scenarios: including narratives, pathways and storylines. Not all share this understanding, and further discussion on scenario definitions may be useful.

Distinguish IPCC assessment language from COP decisions. Several participants spoke to how results from global modelled mitigation pathways are used in climate negotiation. The example reductions of global emissions reduction of 43% by 2030 below 2019 levels was cited many times. Some pointed out that 43% is a median in a wide range. Others argued against making conceptual jumps from scenario logic (“requires for internal consistency”) to prescriptive global targets in COP texts.

Transparently distinguish normative and analytical assumptions. There was broad support for distinguishing normative and analytical assumptions and making both transparent. There is confusion between different kinds of assumptions, normative vs. analytical. Given their importance, there is work to explain technical parameters in models to broader audiences. As a separate matter, it is also important to make clear the normative assumptions and choices made by modelers. Some suggested there is a gap between what modelers think and what they want. While some characterized this as modelers living in bubble (believing their work is neutral), others countered that this misses how many modelers think carefully, beyond the technical and acknowledge criticism. For all, it is helpful to reflect on what could be and what should be.

Scenario makers should convene and engage in conversation to ensure proper interpretation. In addition to making assumptions transparent, it was suggested that modelers and other developers of scenario should take responsibility for their results, and how they are used, and proactively engage in conversations to ensure appropriate use. Merely sending results to be interpreted by others was seen as inadequate by several.

Anticipate political transformations and foreground equity. While it was acknowledged that the modeling community issues *caveats*, it is predictable that results are transformed through negotiations. Scenario makers should foreground equity and normative assumptions, not bury them in technical details.

How do (or how can) modelled scenarios get translated into expectations of countries' mitigation efforts?

Avoid misapplication of global results to national targets. Building on the discussion of how 43% was applied as a global prescription, several participants pointed to similar challenges in relation to net zero emissions. Analysis that finds that global emissions need to be net zero CO₂ by 2050 does not mean each country must adopt a net zero emissions by 2050 goal. Some participants raised the question how to avoid scenario results being used to blame individual countries for exceeding 1.5°C. The consideration of equity was supported by many, meaning that when applying global results to countries consider, one must consider how are different. Equity is an essential aspect of making assumptions explicit.

Claims of individual NDCs' alignment with 1.5°C are not robust. Following on the previous point, a suggestion was to consider differences in time (2035 vs 2100), space (global / national) and equity (since all countries' emissions matter). Others supporting this approach extended it to indicate the political demand for NDCs are "aligned with 1.5" was not based in sound analysis and was further misinterpreted as requiring net zero by 2050 for all countries. Language of alignment of individual countries NDCs with 1.5 is analytically not robust.

Appendix – Discussion Papers Prepared for the Seminar Series

Key considerations for equitable and ambitious climate finance: An international perspective.....	28
National Mitigation Pathways and Fair Share Analysis.....	32
Justice Within Limits: Climate Futures and Adaptive Capacity.....	38
Hope is not a strategy...a practitioner’s viewpoint.....	40
Climate Justice and its Relationship to Other Issues of Justice	45
Wielding the Narrative Knife: Open Questions for Climate Equity Analysts	51
Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) and equity	55
Equity and fairness in the distribution of gains from decarbonization	60

Key considerations for equitable and ambitious climate finance: An international perspective

Recent work highlights the critical intersection of fairness, and the scale of financial flows required to achieve ambitious climate change goals effectively. Current levels of climate finance are grossly insufficient and are not always distributed equitably, hindering both ambition and the achievement of global climate and related development goals. The historical responsibility of developed nations, the urgent need for substantial increases in financial support for developing countries, and the importance of integrating equity principles, including benefit-sharing, human rights, intergenerational equity, and intersectional considerations, are important issues highlighted in recent work.

The critical intersection of equity and ambition in climate finance

The urgency of climate action emphasizes the essential link between equitable climate finance and ambitious policies. Developing nations require fair and sufficient financial support to pursue meaningful action, contribute to global mitigation and adaptation, and address loss and damage in vulnerable communities. Recent studies emphasize that adequate and just climate finance is crucial to achieving global climate goals, in line with the Paris Agreement's principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities and Respective Capabilities (CBDR-RC).

The following are reasons why and how equity in climate finance is essential:

- Enabling ambitious climate action: Many low- and middle-income developing nations (LMICs) lack the resources to implement ambitious climate policies. International financial flows are crucial to supporting emission reductions and enhancing resilience.
- Promoting equity: Climate finance addresses the ecological debt owed by developed nations and ensures a fairer distribution of climate action costs.
- Addressing climate justice: Vulnerable communities and nations bear the brunt of climate change despite contributing the least to its causes. Targeted financial support can help mitigate these disproportionate burdens.
- Facilitating a just transition: Financing is required to transition economies from fossil fuels while ensuring social and economic equity.

Insufficiency of current climate finance flows

Multiple sources, including the IMF and the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report, confirm that current global climate finance flows are grossly inadequate.

Current financial flows fall significantly short of what is required:

- Mitigation finance gap: Financial flows need to increase three to sixfold between 2020-2030 to meet Paris-aligned targets (IPCC 2023). Current climate finance flows amount to about 1% of world GDP. Achieving ambitious temperature targets will require higher overall investment levels, raising the proportion of energy investments in total global GDP from 3% to as much as 5% in the coming decades (Bertram et al., 2021).
- Adaptation finance needs: Adaptation finance required in developing nations is projected to be ten times higher than current levels (UNFCCC 2024).
- Loss and damage funding: The newly established Loss and Damage Fund requires substantial contributions yet remains underfunded.

- Overall investment needs: Developing countries are estimated to require USD 455-584 billion annually to implement their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), yet current finance flows remain insufficient (UNFCCC 2024).

Recent research on required fair international financial flows consistent with Paris Agreement's ambitious LTTG

Recent research indicates that financial flows must scale up dramatically. Pachauri et al (2022) examine modeled estimates of regional mitigation investment needs assessed in WG III's contribution to AR6, focusing on low-carbon energy and energy efficiency improvements. They estimate that approximately USD 250 billion to USD 1.6 trillion annually (2015 values) is required to close the mitigation gap equitably. These flows are essential to bridge the gap between the investment needed for effective mitigation and the fair-share contributions of regions (considering responsibility, capability and needs based principles and indicators). Regardless of the specific combination of equity principles applied, the study underscores the necessity of significantly scaling up interregional financial transfers to ensure a just and effective global climate response (see webtool)

Vinca et al (2025) go beyond traditional cost-effectiveness models by integrating damages, mitigation, and fairness within a single framework. By explicitly accounting for regional inequalities in historical responsibility, economic capability, and climate vulnerability, this research provides a more comprehensive approach to climate finance. It highlights that stringent mitigation efforts, supported by fair financial mechanisms, could significantly reduce global economic damages, potentially halving them by 2050 compared to current trajectories.

Crucially, the findings reveal that fair climate finance benefits all regions, including high-income nations, as proactive investment in mitigation leads to net economic gains. Supporting mitigation efforts in LMICs not only reduces climate risks but also generates economic advantages globally. Furthermore, investing in mitigation now could result in substantial long-term savings in climate finance, alleviating financial pressures on low-emitting regions that would otherwise bear a disproportionate burden.

The study highlights the unequal distribution of climate impacts and mitigation costs, emphasizing that the economic damages of climate change are not borne equally across regions. It explores how responsibility for mitigation costs and loss-and-damage compensation could be allocated using the "polluter pays" principle. Two key approaches are examined: the "proportional approach," which assigns costs based on cumulative CO₂ emissions, and the "carbon debt approach," which requires compensation from countries that have exceeded their fair share of the 1.5°C carbon budget.

Quantifying the scale of financial needs, the research estimates that under current emissions trends, global economic damages could range from \$1.5 trillion to \$7.5 trillion in 2030, with climate finance requirements between \$0.55 trillion and \$4.3 trillion per year. Strategic investments in mitigation could lead to substantial savings, reducing annual climate finance needs by \$0.5 trillion in 2030 and by \$2.5 trillion in 2050. Without such investments, global GDP losses due to climate change are projected to exceed 7% by 2050 and could rise to 40% by 2100.

In terms of financial responsibility, Europe and North America emerge as key contributors to both mitigation and loss-and-damage financing under most scenarios. Meanwhile, regions such as Africa, South Asia, and Latin America are identified as requiring compensation for climate impacts, though they are also expected to contribute to domestic mitigation efforts. The study estimates that loss-and-damage financing needs in 2030

could range between \$58 billion and \$380 billion per year across different Paris-aligned mitigation pathways, further highlighting the urgency of fair financial support.

Emerging conceptual frameworks for equity in climate finance

Recent scholarship has advanced frameworks for understanding and assessing distributive aspects of climate finance.

A recent study develops a framework for evaluating distributive equity in adaptation finance through a comprehensive approach to measuring how climate finance benefits reach vulnerable communities (Shawoo et al., 2024). This work emphasizes that adaptation finance should go beyond just allocation and ensure it reaches the most vulnerable within at-risk countries. To achieve true equity, the authors stress that funding must address root causes of vulnerability, enhance access to resources, support social protections, and uphold human rights.

Benefit-sharing is increasingly recognized as a key tool for achieving equity in climate finance. A recent study explores how benefit-sharing principles can improve the fair distribution of climate finance (Bouwer 2021). The research examines its development as an emerging obligation in both human rights and environmental law, highlighting inconsistencies in its definition and implementation within climate finance. The study argues that establishing clear, universal norms for benefit-sharing could enhance equity in climate finance frameworks.

Human rights frameworks represent another approach gaining traction. A recent study advocates for enhancing climate finance through alignment with international human rights obligations (Albajili et al., 2024). It critiques existing finance mechanisms that perpetuate debt and inequality, instead proposing a legally binding framework that treats climate finance as an obligation to ensure fair and predictable funding flows to the Global South. This approach emphasizes justice and accountability as core principles for effective global adaptation and resilience.

Intergenerational equity considerations have also gained prominence. A recent study examines how ocean-based mitigation and adaptation, finance contribute to intergenerational equity (Morgera et al., 2022). This work connects climate finance discussions to broader obligations toward future generations, and the importance of systemic interpretation of existing international agreements. In other work, a measure “net-zero carbon debt” has been introduced that tracks responsibility for overshoot and the associated additional burdens shifted to future generations (Pelz et al., 2025).

Governance challenges and coordination

The fragmentation of climate finance governance presents significant barriers to ambition. Analysis of climate finance coordination politics highlights how the landscape remains fragmented due to the variety of actors involved at different levels (Lundsgaarde et al., 2021). Improved coordination among over 90 climate-specific funds identified requires careful consideration of the political context and the influences exerted by fund secretariats and external stakeholders.

There are also concerns regarding a lack of standardized accounting rules under the UNFCCC, which has allowed developed countries to define and report climate finance inconsistently. The OECD reported climate finance at \$78.9 billion in 2018, but these figures faced widespread skepticism from developing nations, NGOs, and academics. Inconsistencies in methodologies and definitions have led to starkly different

estimates. For instance, Oxfam’s estimate for 2017–2018 was also far lower than OECD figures (Roberts et al., 2021).

According to Roberts et al. (2021), three key issues drive these discrepancies. First, developed nations often report loans, grants, and investments at face value, ignoring repayment obligations. Second, different countries and institutions apply varying criteria to classify climate-related funding, which leads to inconsistent categorization. Third, the promise of ‘new and additional’ funds remains unresolved, as some climate finance is repurposed from existing development aid rather than increasing overall financial support. These inconsistencies continue to undermine trust and transparency in climate finance reporting.

Summary and outlook

A clear picture of the urgency of scaling up and enhancing the equity of climate finance is evident from recent scholarship on this topic. Current financial flows are insufficient to meet global climate goals and are not always reaching the most vulnerable nations and communities in a fair manner. Addressing structural inequalities, improving governance and coordination, fully operationalizing the Loss and Damage Fund, and learning from successful models like the Kigali Amendment¹ are crucial steps. Developed nations must significantly increase their financial contributions, recognizing their historical responsibility, while ensuring that finance is allocated based on principles of responsibility, capability, and need. Unequal power dynamics between different levels of government and between authorities and vulnerable communities need to be overcome to improve distributive and procedural justice within countries as well. There is also a need for greater recognition that a commitment to equitable climate finance is not only a matter of justice but also a pragmatic necessity for achieving ambitious climate action and minimizing global economic damages.

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1 The Multilateral Fund (MLF), is a key financial mechanism supporting the Kigali Amendment, providing financial assistance to developing countries for compliance with phasedown commitments. It has funded technology transitions, capacity- building, and policy implementation in developing nations, enabling equitable participation.

National Mitigation Pathways and Fair Share Analysis

1. Definitions

- “Fair Shares” – generally defines shares, here: specifically related to mitigation, of a global mitigation pathway or an emissions budget, that are consistent with “fairness” as expressed by a chosen set of equity principles and a concrete implementation of these principles.
- “National Mitigation Pathways” – here, is taken to mean, first and foremost, national mitigation pathways that would be consistent with the fair shares as defined above. However, “national mitigation pathways” often is also used to refer to actual emission pathways that nations would follow under other considerations (e.g. cost-efficiency, heuristic downscaling, ..) and that typically are different from those consistent with fair shares. Here, those latter pathways are called “physical [national] emissions pathways.”

2. Starting Point

There is a mature body of literature that considers fair shares of global mitigation and/or global carbon budgets. Many of us contribute to that literature. IPCC AR5¹ suggested that much of the then-existing literature on effort sharing fits into one or more of six categories of approaches (responsibility, capability, equality, responsibility-capability-need, equal-cumulative-per-capita, “staged”).

This two pager is not the place to review this literature, though it’s perhaps good to recall that: 1) studies often stress that there is no universally agreed vision of “fairness”; 2) studies come to vastly different results, depending on the “fairness” concept used; 3) as a group, existing studies tend to focus on a subset of relevant “pattern of justice”² or/and specific fairness considerations, with others remaining underexamined;³ 4) studies’ quantifications of “fair shares”-compliant “national mitigation pathways” are typically not conceptualized as “physical emissions pathways,” thus requiring additional considerations to reconcile the two (typically exogenous to the study); 5) studies vary in the degree to which they problematize/disclose/discuss the normative assumptions (and their implications) that they make and/or “import” from underlying other studies.

3. Areas for discussion

How does the large range of results impact utility of “fair shares” analyses?

Given that different studies use very different conceptualizations of “fairness” in investigating national mitigation pathways consistent with these fairness conceptualizations, they arrive at vastly different results (see exhibit A in the annex). In fact, the results vary so much that even if all countries would follow national mitigation pathways consistent with some study’s “fair shares” under a given global mitigation target, the sum of these national pathways would exceed the global pathway under that target (see exhibit B). Does that

1 Leon Clarke et al., “Chapter 6: Assessing Transformation Pathways,” in *Climate Change 2014: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, ed. IPCC (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), <http://mitigation2014.org/report/final-draft>.

2 Caroline Zimm et al., “Justice Considerations in Climate Research,” *Nature Climate Change* 14, no. 1 (January 2024): 22–30, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-023-01869-0>.

3 Kate Dooley et al., “Ethical Choices Behind Quantifications of Fair Contributions Under the Paris Agreement,” *Nature Climate Change* 11(2021):300–305, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01015-8>.

effect limit or undermine the usefulness of these undertakings and if so, what (if anything) could be done about it?

How can “fair shares” studies better deal with the tension between national “fair shares” mitigation pathways and “physical emissions pathways”?

It is clear from our own experience, as well as others, that “users” of fair shares analysis are not only (or, potentially, not even primarily) interested in national “fair shares” mitigation pathways, but rather in (equity- or fairness-informed) pathways that correspond directly (or, at least, more directly) to “physical emissions pathways.” Different studies or projects address this in different ways. For example, Climate Action Tracker’s “overall rating” is now mostly based on “modelled domestic pathways” (national pathways downscaled from modelled global pathways), the Climate Equity Reference Calculator shows an “indicative” physical emissions pathway based on a simple heuristic (exhibit C), whereas civil society “users” of the Climate Equity Reference framework define their own domestic physical emissions pathways (sometimes based on their own bottom up modelling, like in the case of Climate Action Network Canada – see exhibit D).

Several issues arise from this. First, any downscaling of physical emissions pathways from global or regional pathways “imports” the normative dimensions, often deep and substantial, of the underlying (global or regional) pathways and/or of the metrics used for downscaling, which are often left unaddressed or even undocumented or unacknowledged. For example, downscaling using GDP or population projections that perpetuate existing inequalities and suffering, or emissions baselines that are based on (partial) perpetuation of wasteful consumption patterns and unsustainable lifestyles. On the other hand, even where nationally-specific bottom-up physical emissions pathways are used (e.g. in the Canadian example in exhibit D), those have their own normatively relevant assumptions that may be inconsistent with the fair shares analysis they are paired with.

Second, national “fair shares” mitigation pathways often not matching (plausible?, realistic?, necessary?) national physical emissions pathways results in a misalignment that, to still comply with a given global mitigation pathway or emissions budget, requires some countries to follow physical emissions pathways that are more demanding than their national “fair shares” mitigation pathways would be, if other countries are to be “allowed” less stringent ones (exemplified by South Africa and Canada, respectively, in exhibit C). It is an open question how to best conceptualize this misalignment. For example, the IPCC AR5 summary of the effort sharing literature at that point conceptualized the difference as trading of emissions allowances (which brings in the related, problematic area of emissions “rights” – see below),⁴ whereas other approaches point toward the moral obligation of the latter group of countries to (financially and otherwise) support additional mitigation in the former group,⁵ with some studies attempting to quantify the costs of this additional mitigation for countries.⁶

Finally, anecdotal experience shows that where “fair shares” analyses provide benchmarks for both national “fair shares” mitigation pathways and physical emissions pathways, there exists a risk that users mistake the latter for the former. Remaining with the same example, in research and communication around Canada’s

4 Clarke et al., “Chapter 6: Assessing Transformation Pathways.”

5 Ceecee Holz, Sivan Kartha, and Tom Athanasiou, “Fairly Sharing 1.5 – National Fair Shares of a 1.5°C- Compliant Global Mitigation Effort,” *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics* 18, no. Special Issue: Achieving 1.5°C and Climate Justice (2018): 117–34, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10784-017-9371-z>.

6 Ceecee Holz, “Canada’s Fair Share of 1.5 °C-Consistent Global Mitigation Through 2035” (Climate Equity Reference Project, March 26, 2024), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2595506>; Ceecee Holz, Tom Athanasiou, and Sivan Kartha, “La Juste Part de La France Dans La Lutte Contre Les Changements Climatiques,” *Serie de Documents de Travail de Climate Equity Reference Project* WP008-FR (2022), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2595500>.

fair share,⁷ Canadian civil society organizations characterized their own work's physical emissions pathway (60% reduction) as the country's fair share, rather than what they had actually determined Canada's national "fair share" mitigation pathway to be (140%) (see exhibit D). Likewise, anecdotal experience suggests that many users of the Climate Action Tracker's NDC ratings understand those ratings as ratings based on "fair shares" analysis alone, whereas in reality the non-fair shared components of CAT's methodology have a stronger impact on the results.^{8,9} Does this misalignment between the real-world interpretations and uses of "fair shares" by its users represent a fundamental problem for this type of studies? And if so, what can be done to address it?

What can be done about the dominance of certain equity perspectives in effort sharing literature?

The effort sharing literature is dominated by only a small subset of justice/equity concepts. This includes 1) the inclusion in studies of equity concepts that are seen by some as problematic (for example, "equal per capita" approaches or "grandfathering," sometimes renamed "sovereignty" or "constant emissions ratio"), often in ways that are not immediately transparent to readers or users, for example as part of a composite indicator or via transition periods from one allocation principle to another.^{10,11} Perhaps more problematically, 2) many important justice concepts have thus far been left out of quantitative effort sharing studies (for example, "the relative moral relevance of consumption-based versus production-based emissions, survival versus luxury emissions, progressive versus regressive allocation of mitigation costs, prioritarianism versus egalitarianism and finally [...] the right to development and the critical ethical importance of the eradication of poverty"¹²). Finally, 3) effort sharing studies often build on other work that has its own, explicit and implicit, equity-relevant assumptions and choices, often across several steps, that are typically left undisclosed, undiscussed and unaddressed.

Other questions

Additional questions can be asked that are relevant, but don't neatly fit into the thematic areas above. Some of them have potential for interesting synergies with other session topics.

First, as mentioned above, the way misalignment between national "fair share" mitigation pathways and physical emissions pathways is often conceptualized is via (tradable) emissions rights, where the national fair shares pathways are thought of as representing allocations of emissions rights (and their trading would result in alignment with the physical emissions pathways). The idea of "rights" to emissions has been widely criticized, given the well-established adverse impacts and resultant harm of GHG emissions. Thus, to the degree that effort-sharing studies (given the almost inevitable misalignment mentioned above) rely on (at

7 CAN-Rac Canada et al., "Towards Canada's Fair Share. New Research on Achieving a Stronger Climate Target," 2021, <https://environmentaldefence.ca/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Towards-Canadas-Fair-Share-May-2021.pdf>.

8 See the discussion of the CAT methodology and the relationship between effort-sharing and other dimension in the overall assessment results in: Ceecee Holz, "Are G20 Countries Doing Their Fair Share of Global Climate Mitigation? Comparing Ambition and Fair Shares Assessments of G20 Countries' Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs)" (Oxford: Oxfam International, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.21201/2023.621540>.

9 Additional examples of users and media misunderstanding and/or misrepresenting results and outputs of effort sharing studies come to mind (e.g. The Guardian's write up of Robiou du Pont and Meinshausen's 2018 "Warming Assessment" article; and others) and can be discussed as well.

10 Dooley et al., "Ethical Choices Behind Quantifications of Fair Contributions Under the Paris Agreement."

11 Sivan Kartha et al., "Cascading Biases Against Poorer Countries," *Nature Climate Change* 8, no. 5 (2018): 348–49, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0152-7>

12 Kartha et al.

least theoretically) the concept of the creation of such rights, they have to content with this criticism, or articulate alternatives.

Second, effort sharing literature focusses on interrogating *national* fair shares of global mitigation efforts and/or emissions budgets. As such, they typically have limited insights in the implications of effort sharing on different potential units of analysis than the nation state, which might be more instructive, relevant or insightful. Examples for such alternative units of analysis include sub- national analysis for specific emitting sectors, for regions within countries, and perhaps most relevantly, for specific socio-economic groups within countries (or potentially even the individual). Part of the question here is whether the nation state is (still) the most relevant unit of analysis for effort sharing studies.

Third, effort sharing studies typically tread a unit of GHG emission (or mitigation) as perfectly equivalent to every other unit of GHG emission (or mitigation), whereas in reality there are substantial differences in terms of emissions' (or mitigation's) implications for normatively relevant dynamics such as development or human welfare. To illustrate with an extreme example: clearly, CO₂ molecule emitted from a kerosene lamp that illuminates the homework sheet of a child that lives in a remote village with no electric light, while having the same impact on climate change, is qualitatively very different from a CO₂ molecule emitted during a billionaire's private leisure space flight. Should effort sharing studies account for these differences and if so, how?

Exhibits

Exhibit A: Table from Oxfam¹³ study comparing fairness assessments of the NDCs (for 2030) of G20 countries by Climate Action Tracker (CAT), Climate Equity Reference Project (CERP) approach, (and equal consumption CO₂ emissions per capita), illustrating how different approaches come to substantially different results – with the two CAT approaches generally yielding “better” assessments for higher-income countries in the sample and “worse” assessments for the lower-income countries, with the reverse being the case for the other approaches. (note, while these three approaches also somewhat differ in their quantification of the mitigation targets of the NDCs, the difference in assessments mostly stems from differences in the “benchmarks” against which the mitigation targets are evaluated)

Table 2: Comparison of Assessment Approaches for all G20 countries. Note: Table is sorted by average rank across approaches

	Equal consumption CO ₂ per capita	CERP fair share	CAT effort sharing	CAT hybrid
United States	exceeds by more than 4 times	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
Russia	exceeds by more than 4 times	exceeds by less than 10t/cap	Critically insufficient	Critically insufficient
Australia	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
Germany	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
South Korea	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by less than 5t/cap	Highly insufficient	Highly insufficient
Saudi Arabia	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by less than 10t/cap	Critically insufficient	Highly insufficient
Japan	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
Türkiye	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by less than 5t/cap	Critically insufficient	Critically insufficient
Canada	exceeds by less than 4 times	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Highly insufficient
United Kingdom	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Almost sufficient
European Union	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by less than 10t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
Italy	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by less than 10t/cap	Missing	Missing
France	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by more than 10t/cap	Missing	Missing
China	exceeds by less than 4 times	1.5°C fair share compliant	Highly insufficient	Highly insufficient
Indonesia	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by less than 5t/cap	Critically insufficient	Highly insufficient
Mexico	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by less than 5t/cap	Critically insufficient	Highly insufficient
Argentina	exceeds by less than double	exceeds by less than 1t/cap	Highly insufficient	Highly insufficient
Brazil	1.5°C consistent	exceeds by less than 5t/cap	Insufficient	Insufficient
India	1.5°C consistent	exceeds by less than 11t/cap	Insufficient	Highly insufficient
South Africa	exceeds by less than 1/4	1.5°C fair share compliant	Insufficient	Insufficient

13 Holz, Ceecee (2023) “Are G20 Countries Doing Their Fair Share of Global Climate Mitigation? Comparing Ambition and Fair Shares Assessments of G20 Countries’ Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).” <https://doi.org/10.21201/2023.621540>

Exhibit B: Chart from Meinshausen et. al 2015 “Diversity-Aware Leadership” article,¹⁴ which illustrates the effect of exceeding the collective target *even if* all countries self-select a target- consistent national fair share that is consistent with fair shares analysis under different approaches with vastly different results.

Figure 3 | Illustration of the ‘diversity-aware leadership’ concept in contrast with self-differentiation. a, Self-differentiation under a joint target C leads to the collective target C being exceeded.

Exhibit C: “Country Report” charts for Canada and South Africa from the Climate Equity Reference Calculator (calculator.climateequityreference.org) illustrating the difference between national “fair shares” mitigation pathways (solid blue line) and an illustrative physical emissions pathways (dotted green line, here downscaled from the global mitigation pathways by applying the global below-baseline reduction rate to each national baseline).

Country/region report in 2030 for Canada

Show settings

Country/region report in 2030 for South Africa

Show settings

14 Malte Meinshausen et al., “National Post-2020 Greenhouse Gas Targets and Diversity-Aware Leadership,” *Nature Climate Change* 5 (October 26, 2015): 1098–1106, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2826>.

Exhibit D: Climate Action Network Canada’s “fair shares” infographic (excerpt) showing the disaggregation of the total national “fair share” mitigation pathway into a “physical emissions pathway” component and a “international support” component.¹⁵

15 CAN-Rac Canada, “Canada’s Fair Share Towards Limiting Global Warming to 1.5°C. Infographic” (Ottawa: Climate Action Network Canada, 2019), <https://climateactionnetwork.ca/2019/12/02/canadas-fair-share-towards-limiting-global-warming-to-1-5c/>.

Justice Within Limits: Climate Futures and Adaptive Capacity

Abstract. This think piece examines adaptation limits through the lens of capabilities, offering a justice-based perspective on adaptation research, modelling and policy. While existing literature has explored adaptive capacity and adaptation limits, the justice dimensions of these limits—particularly soft limits, where adaptation becomes increasingly difficult due to structural inequalities—remain underdeveloped. Drawing on Amartya Sen’s capabilities approach, the piece reframes soft limits not as implementation barriers but as constraints on people’s freedoms to respond to climate risks. It also considers how maladaptation can increase the risk of reaching soft limits. Adaptation justice requires asking who can adapt, who decides, and under what constraints.

Keywords: climate change adaptation, adaptation justice, adaptation limits, mitigation pathways, adaptive capacity, capabilities approach, maladaptation.

1. Adaptation Limits

As climate change accelerates, the concept of adaptation limits has become increasingly central to both research and policy. These limits can be understood in two ways. Limits *of* adaptation refer to hard thresholds: points at which climate impacts overwhelm the possibility of further adjustment. These are often driven by the magnitude and pace of change, shaped in turn by global mitigation pathways. Limits *to* adaptation, by contrast, are soft limits: they reflect constraints on capacity, such as insufficient resources, weak governance, or social and political marginalisation. These limits do not mark the end of adaptation *per se*, but rather its growing difficulty or ineffectiveness.

The justice implications of hard limits are increasingly addressed through debates around loss and damage, which link inadequate mitigation to irreversible harms. In contrast, the justice dimensions of soft limits remain underexplored. This think piece considers both dimensions, but places particular emphasis on who faces soft limits, why, and with what consequences. Drawing on Amartya Sen’s capabilities approach and earlier work on adaptive capacity, it reframes soft limits not merely as technical or institutional challenges, but as the product of deeper structural inequalities. In doing so, it positions adaptation justice as a question not only of what is technically or financially possible, but of whose futures remain viable in a warming world, and whose do not.

2. Capacity and Capabilities

Adaptation limits do not emerge in a vacuum. They are shaped by choices made today, including about how rapidly the world reduces greenhouse gas emissions. Lower levels of mitigation ambition are associated with more severe, widespread and nonlinear impacts, increasing the likelihood that communities will encounter hard adaptation limits. But mitigation ambition also affects the distribution and intensity of soft limits, by determining not just how much adaptation is needed, but where, by whom, and under what constraints. Soft limits can be framed in terms of adaptive capacity: the ability of individuals, communities and institutions to adjust to climate risks, reorganize in response to change, and seize emerging opportunities. Yet this framing often obscures more than it reveals. Treated as a technical variable, adaptive capacity is typically measured through indicators such as income, education, infrastructure or institutional quality. These metrics can be useful, but they do not account for the political, historical and structural conditions that shape freedoms to adapt. Nor do they answer the critical question: whose capacity counts, and who decides?

Amartya Sen's capabilities approach offers a more ethically grounded lens through which to understand adaptive capacity. Rather than focusing solely on resources or outcomes, Sen argues that justice should be assessed in terms of the freedoms people have to live the lives they value. From this perspective, adaptation is not only about responding to environmental risks, but about safeguarding the conditions that allow individuals and communities to exercise agency and pursue meaningful futures. This reframing draws attention to the uneven distribution of those freedoms and to the social, political and economic structures that constrain them. In this light, soft limits are not simply technical or institutional shortcomings; they are manifestations of deeper injustices that restrict people's capabilities to adapt on their own terms.

Maladaptation further complicates this picture. Efforts to adapt, especially when designed without meaningful local participation or pursued as ad-hoc and siloed interventions, can reinforce existing inequalities or shift risks onto others. In contexts where adaptive capacity is already constrained, such responses may increase the risk of reaching soft limits rather than alleviating them. A justice-oriented perspective on adaptation must therefore consider not only who is unable to adapt, but also how adaptation itself can entrench or redistribute vulnerability.

3. Conclusions

Adaptation justice begins with the recognition that limits—both hard and soft—are not neutral thresholds, but outcomes of political, economic and social choices. Mitigation ambition influences not only the scale of climate impacts, but also the extent to which adaptation remains possible at all. Yet even where adaptation is technically and financially feasible, soft limits persist. These are shaped by structural inequalities that constrain the freedoms people have to respond, reorganise and recover in the face of climate disruption. By linking the capabilities approach with adaptation policy, I reframe soft limits as more than barriers to implementation. They are indicators of whose voices are excluded, whose vulnerabilities are ignored, and whose futures are placed at risk. Addressing adaptation limits through a justice lens therefore requires more than solutions that treat adaptation as a technical exercise. It demands attention to power, to agency, and to the conditions under which people can meaningfully shape their responses to climate change. In the end, the question is not just what we can adapt to, but who gets to adapt, and on what terms.

Discussion Questions

1. How are adaptation limits currently represented—or omitted—in integrated assessment models? What assumptions underlie these representations?
2. In scenarios with lower mitigation ambition, how are assumptions about future adaptation needs and capacities handled? Do such assumptions risk shifting the burden of climate response onto those least able to bear it?
3. What are the implications of shifting from adaptive capacity to capabilities for understanding and modelling adaptation? Can models meaningfully address questions of agency, constraint, and justice?
4. What distinguishes capacity-building from pursuing justice in adaptation? What is lost when adaptive capacity is treated as a purely technical or economic variable?
5. How do modelling frameworks, policy tools or funding mechanisms unintentionally reinforce maladaptation—for example, by favouring technocratic or top-down solutions? How can justice be more effectively accounted for in these systems?
6. How can global mitigation and adaptation goals be aligned with the lived realities of those facing soft limits today? What role can narratives, models and scenarios play in making these limits visible?

Hope is not a strategy...a practitioner's viewpoint

I have spent over 30 years working as a local level practitioner, using science to engage with the day-to-day opportunities and problems in Africa's cities. Those experiences have made me an advocate for what I refer to as "radical realism", i.e. the need to look beyond theory and hope to the reality on the ground. This is especially so when it comes to climate change.

There is no doubt that the 2015 Paris Agreement marked an important milestone in addressing the climate crisis. But it has also proved to be a double-edged sword. The commitment to "*pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels*" has been effective in driving change in policy and action at all levels, but it has also created political inertia and unwillingness to talk about the possibility that this aspirational objective might not be met. International leaders still repeat the call to "*keep 1.5 alive*" in order to sustain hope of an ambitious climate change response in international negotiations. As a result, there is a growing dissonance between what science is saying - a decade on from the Paris Agreement - and what we are prepared to talk about as a society. But hope is not a strategy, and we should not remain stuck in the past. The Paris Agreement should not be seen as a Peter Pan agreement.

As a practitioner, common sense has taught me the importance of distinguishing between what is desirable and what can get done. Given the mounting scientific evidence, common sense suggests that there is a growing and urgent need to discuss the possibility of temperature goal overshoot (>1.5°C, >2.0°C)¹¹ and its implications for development, equity, justice, sustainable development and fair ambition. Overshoot changes the context and pathways for what we might consider a just transition. It raises questions about what will be fair in a >1.5°C world. Not to have such a discussion is simply irresponsible if we consider the following:

- The atmospheric concentration of carbon dioxide has continued to increase and in 2024 reached a record level of [422.1 ppm](#) (+2.9ppm on 2023).
- Despite the dramatic increase in the availability and use of renewable energy, fossil fuels still met [80% of global energy demand](#) in 2023.
- [UNEP's 2024 Emissions Gap Report](#) concluded that "*nations must deliver dramatically stronger ambition and action in the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions or the Paris Agreement's 1.5°C goal will be gone within a few years.*" The failure to increase ambition in the new Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) would put the world on course for a temperature increase of 2.6-3.1°C over the course of this century.
- [UNEP's 2023 Production Gap Report](#) showed that governments, in aggregate, still plan to produce more than double the amount of fossil fuels in 2030 than would be consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C.
- [UNEP's 2024 Adaptation Gap Report](#) points to the fact that the adaptation gap is not closing, and that adaptation finance lags behind needs.
- Oil majors like BP and Shell are [renewing their focus on oil and gas](#), seeking to achieve better returns after fossil fuel prices bounced back from pandemic lows, and Russia's invasion of Ukraine.
- [The International Energy Agency](#) (2024) reported that coal consumption is now on track to rise to a new peak of 8.77bn tonnes by the end of the year (2024) – and could remain at near-record levels until 2027.

11 Overshoot is defined by the IPCC as a situation where a particular global warming level is exceeded and where there is a return to or below that level again before the end of a specified period of time (e.g., before 2100).

- The latest “[Carbon Majors Database](#)” report by climate think tank InfluenceMap shows that many of the world’s largest emitters increased their emissions in 2023 compared to the previous year, with the cement industry being a significant contributor due to its energy-intensive processes.
- The [IPCC’s Sixth Assessment report](#) (2023) showed that if we are to limit global warming to 1.5°C with no or limited overshoot, global emissions would need to be 43% below 2019 levels in 2030 and 60% below 2019 levels in 2035. But a [report prepared by the UNFCCC Secretariat](#) in 2024 prior to COP29 showed that even if current Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) are fully implemented, emissions in 2030 are still projected to reach 51.5 gigatonnes of CO₂ equivalent - a reduction of only 2.6% from 2019 levels.
- There is no indication of the level of the ambition in the [new NDCs](#) as most countries have missed a deadline to update their NDCs by 10 February 2025.
- The possibility of temperature reversal following overshoot is also being questioned e.g. [Schleussner et al., 2024](#) suggest that “*temperature reversal could be undercut by strong Earth- system feedbacks resulting in high near-term and continuous long-term warming*”.
- Such feedbacks are already being detected e.g. [NOAA’s Arctic Report Card \(2024\)](#) shows that the Arctic tundra has already moved from being a carbon sink to a carbon source.
- Similarly, several recent papers show that the rate of natural sequestration of CO₂ from the atmosphere by the terrestrial biosphere [is now declining](#), having reached [a peak in 2008](#) and that as a result atmospheric CO₂ concentration will now rise more rapidly than previously in proportion to annual global CO₂ emissions.
- A number of papers point to the growing implausibility of limiting global warming to 1.5°C (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.1177/29768659241293218>; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02247-8>; <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-025-02246-9>)
- A recent paper by [Hansen et al. \(2025\)](#) suggests that even limiting global warming to 2°C may be impossible. While this finding is contested by some in the scientific community it is certainly not improbable.
- The [USA’s exit from the Paris Agreement](#) for the second time and [standing down from the board of the loss and damage fund](#) suggests that the “whole of society” approach outlined by the IPCC as necessary to limiting global warming to 1.5°C cannot be met over the timelines required.

Current observations also confirm we are heading in the wrong direction if limiting global warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels is the objective:

- The [Copernicus Climate Change Service \(C3S\)](#) indicated that 2024 is the first calendar year to reach more than 1.5°C above the pre-industrial level; for ERA5 it was 1.6°C above pre-industrial levels. The [World Meteorological Organisation \(WMO\)](#) confirmed 2024 as warmest year on record at about 1.55°C above the pre-industrial level.
- Both organisations indicated that each of the past 10 years (2015–2024) was one of the 10 warmest years on record.

One doesn’t have to be a (rocket) scientist to see there is a problem. While the IPCC indicates that temperatures averaged over two or three decades are needed to confirm temperature overshoot, all the indications are that overshoot cannot be ruled out. As noted by [Glen Peters \(2024\)](#) “*It is always possible to find arguments to make 1.5°C forever possible, but they increasingly diverge from reality. It is time to admit that the world will cross 1.5°C and the likelihood of returning below 1.5°C via overshoot is slim...*”

If one accepts there is a reasonable possibility of exceeding global warming of 1.5°C, then it is important to understand the implications for development at the local and global level – a key concern of practitioners - especially in the global South/Majority World. Development remains a central pillar of the global agenda

(most recently through Agenda 2030 and the Sustainable Development Goals). This is unsurprising given that billions of people still need to be lifted out of poverty and that political success/survival is often linked to service and infrastructure delivery. The [IPCC's Special Report on global warming of 1.5 °C](#) made it clear that exceeding 1.5°C would mean an increase in the risks, impacts, and losses and damages experienced by all systems, sectors and regions. This means that practitioners need to think about how to deal with expanded and/or new risk landscapes and how these impact or exacerbate development needs and influence the ability to achieve just transitions and fair ambition.

1. The [IPCC in its sixth assessment report](#) highlighted that every increment of warming increases risks and vulnerability in human and natural communities and contributes to growing inequity and injustice around the world. But overshooting a global warming level of 1.5 °C also brings with it potential adaptation limits (soft and hard), insufficient freshwater for people to continue living on some islands and mountains, irreversible loss of species and ecosystems (that are already at risk at 1.3 °C of warming), dangerous feedbacks in the climate system, unavoidable sea level rise and severe infrastructure damage in low-lying coastal settlements. The accompanying compound and cascading risks will undermine development prospects globally, but especially for the poor and vulnerable.

How do adaptation limits and increasing losses and damages factor into what counts as fair ambition?

2. Poor and vulnerable communities will not only have to deal with the “pain of overshoot”, but also the “pain of transition” i.e. attempts to return to 1.5°C through e.g. Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS); Afforestation; Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) and geo-engineering interventions. This perfect storm of temperature overshoot, rapidly accelerated mitigation efforts, the breaching of adaptation limits, economic and non-economic impacts and escalating loss and damage interacting with unresolved inequities created by poverty, injustice, conflict and factors such as colonialism (past and current) mean that even existing development gains could be reversed and the poor and vulnerable further marginalised. We already live in a world where a [2024 World Bank report](#) dubbed “The Great Reversal” indicates that half of the world’s poorest 75 countries are getting poorer and are seeing a reversal of existing development gains – greatly limiting the prospects for enhancing resilience. There can never be fair ambition in a world polarised between over- and under-development. Development performance should therefore be a key aim of the climate change response, and fair ambition should include enhanced development.

How does fair ambition enable us to change the narrative from climate responses with development co-benefits to development with climate co-benefits to better align with priorities on the ground?

3. An overshoot scenario also raises critical and strategic questions about which climate change response options will remain fit for purpose, become ineffective or emerge as essential given the changing context. What radical restructuring, replacement or abandonment of systems, processes and practices may be required because they are no longer viable under new climatic conditions? It is clear we need to think not only about the impacts of climate change but also [climate change responses](#). For example, [nature based solutions](#) (particularly important in

enhancing adaptive capacity in the global South/Majority World) will be under increased pressure and demonstrate declining effectiveness or irreversible loss because of the impact on species and ecosystems. If nature-based solutions are compromised or no longer effective in reducing risk and enhancing resilience, what sort of grey infrastructure replacements are required to protect lives and livelihoods, what is their cost, and who will they serve? Will local level communities be enabled to deal with this additional developmental pressure through enhanced technical, political and financial support? Would such interventions be sustainable in the longer term? Overshoot raises deep questions about the extent to which there will be synergies or trade-offs between climate responses, development needs and equity and justice imperatives. Given the potential for winners and losers, fair ambition under these circumstances could be very different depending on whose development gains/needs were impacted by climate responses and how they are impacted. A regional perspective is also critical as the impacts and responses to overshoot are not going to be felt equally around the world.

How will the impacts of climate change responses be considered in determining what is considered 'fair ambition'?

4. Timescale is another important consideration. According to the best-case scenario (i.e. very low GHG emissions SSP1-1.9) presented in the [IPCC AR6 reports](#), global surface temperature could increase by up to 1.8°C this century. If overshoot cannot be avoided ([current suggestions](#) are that we could go into overshoot as early as 2029) it would be ideal to return to 1.5°C global warming as soon as possible, but certainly by the end of the century (recalling that reversibility may not be possible). That suggests that two to three generations of people would live and work in a >1.5°C world. What challenges will they face as win-win scenarios are replaced by win-lose scenarios? What are the implications in different geographies, at different levels of regional warming, at different stages of development, over different timelines, and in different sectors of the economy, formal and informal? How will overshoot play out in cities, in informal settlements, in livelihoods stretched across rural-urban areas, how will it affect women and children? How do we adapt to a warming level of >1.5°C while simultaneously delivering on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their successors? Who are the possible losers (human and natural communities) and what safety nets are needed to ensure equity and justice across generations during overshoot? In the medium term (2030 to 2050), development remains a critical safety net and fair ambition will need to focus on supporting development and securing human wellbeing in the context of overshoot. This will include efforts to sustain development gains but also to address persistent development deficits.

There is also the need to consider that climate change responses and development measures that are appropriate for a global warming of 1.5–2°C may lock in development processes that are not viable under greater levels of warming. For example, investment in infrastructure and services in areas that become unproductive or uninhabitable or when thresholds are crossed in terms of water availability, ecosystem viability, human habitability or physiological limits. Alternatively, measures to reduce vulnerability and exposure in the short term may lock in development practices that are unsustainable in areas that are already marginal, increasing future climate risks and undermining development gains.

How do we consider the concept of ‘fair ambition’ not only from the perspective of intragenerational equity but also intergenerational equity?

5. It is also critical to think about the emergence of new developmentally linked tipping points (e.g. 1.5°C overshoot and 3 billion people living in informal settlements in 2050) as well as confounding factors such as aging populations and the breakdown of multilateralism when defining fair ambition.

What will ‘fair ambition’ look like in a world where novel tipping points have changed the operating context entirely?

Concluding thoughts...while the need to discuss 1.5°C overshoot could be seen as a failure of the Paris Agreement it should be seen as a call for even greater development ambition and action. In response there should be a global call to begin preparing plans to deal with overshoot alongside existing plans for achieving 1.5°C/net zero.² It is time to recognise that overshoot requires a new development pathway – one specifically geared to deliver during a suboptimal time of crisis. What is ‘fair’ during a period of overshoot will ultimately have to be measured in terms of human wellbeing and development performance.

Time’s up. The era of wishful thinking is over.

2 Unfortunately, current science is likely to be of limited use to local level practitioners in preparing such plans (especially in the Global South/Majority World) as it is not available at a scale that is appropriate for local level decision making, nor is it decision worthy in the face of accelerating threat.

Climate Justice and its Relationship to Other Issues of Justice

This short note addresses the following set of questions:

To what extent should attempts to implement a just response to climate change seek to address other kinds of injustice too? Should climate policies focus solely and exclusively on climate change? Or, alternatively, may policymakers use climate policies to address other kinds of injustice?

I: Justice and Climate Policies

To answer this set of questions, it is helpful to start by being clear on what questions should come under the heading of 'climate justice'. Climate change raises a number of questions of justice:

- *Just Target*: First, for example, is the question: What should be the target of global mitigation policies? This question cannot be settled by scientific assessments alone (Oppenheimer 2005). It requires ethical criteria – ones that specify what is owed to the potential victims of climate change. What level of protection are they entitled to?
- *Intergenerational Justice*: Given the long-term climatic impacts of emitting greenhouse gases answering the first question requires considering, among other things, what current generations owe to future generations. So it involves questions of intergenerational justice.
- *Justice, Risk and Safety*: In addition to this, determining what climate targets to aim for also requires identifying what is a fair level of risk. This is necessary to specify the size of any 'carbon budget'.
- *Just Carbon Budget*: A just response to climate change also raises the question: How should any remaining 'carbon budget' be distributed? What distributive criteria should guide the distribution?
- *Rights to Extract*? A further distinct, but related, question of justice is: How should any remaining rights to extract fossil fuels be distributed? To the extent that extraction of fossil fuels is morally permissible, who may extract them and how should any such opportunities be distributed (Kantha et al 2018)?
- *Just Burden Sharing*: More generally, societies need to confront the questions: How should the costs (and benefits) of mitigation and adaptation be shared? And, who should pay for 'loss and damage'?
- *Just Transition*: Many emphasize a 'just' transition but what makes a transition 'just'? What criteria must it satisfy?
- *Just Energy Policies*: Decarbonizing the planet requires using other energy sources, and electrification (among other things). Renewables can involve great benefits but some renewable policies can impose costs and harms. We must then consider: What is a just renewables policy? What principles of justice should regulate the extraction of minerals needed for batteries (Sovacool 2020; Sovacool et al 2021)?¹

Bearing all of these in mind, the question this note addresses is whether policymakers confronting these sorts of questions should design climate policies that focus exclusively on climate change. Or should they design climate policies with a view to promoting (domestic or global) justice more generally? Should climate policy limit itself to climate alone? Or may it – should it – have a broader focus?

II: Isolation or Integration?

We can distinguish between two kinds of approach to this question. Some might adopt an *Isolationist* approach. This holds that we should treat climate change *in isolation from* all other policy areas and issues

1 For a fuller discussion of 'climate justice' and the many different questions of justice raised by climate change see Caney (2020).

of justice (such as trade, aid, migration, development, health, biodiversity loss, ozone depletion, food security, among others). We should, on this view, bracket out all other non-climate related issues (Caney 2012).

A second approach (*Integrationism*) denies this. It holds that we should treat climate change in conjunction with other policy areas and issues of justice, and should take into account how climate policies impact on other policy areas (Caney 2012).

A fully isolationist position seems quite implausible. For example, mitigation policies will obviously very often have profound effects on jobs, livelihoods, the cost of living for consumers, some people's investments and pensions, people's health, and so on. It would be quite irresponsible to make climate policy without taking into account these effects.

In addition to this, if we consider the global level, it is imperative that the world's least advantaged are able to develop and attain a decent standard of living. Any burdens of mitigation and adaptation must, then, be allocated in ways that do not set back the capacity of the poor to develop (Caney 2010; Moellendorf 2014). Furthermore, governments must ensure that renewables policies do not impose burdens and wrongs on the most disadvantaged. They should not, for example, adopt solar, wind or hydroelectric policies that deprive indigenous peoples of their land; they should not extract lithium (and other minerals needed for batteries and electric vehicles) in ways that deny people access to water, or threaten their health (Sovacool et al 2020; Sovacool 2021). In other words, climate policies should not undermine people's rights to land, water, food, health, and to develop.

On this basis, we might say that policymakers have a *negative duty* not to impose unjust costs and harms on the world's vulnerable and disadvantaged. Climate policies (mitigation, adaptation and loss and damage) should not exacerbate other injustices. They should not make other injustices worse. The question, though, remains as to whether there is a *positive duty* to construct climate policies that promote justice in these other policy areas. That is, is there a positive duty to promote justice more generally? In what follows I set out some reasons for thinking that there is and then add several qualifications.

III: Three Arguments

§1. Positive Duties of Justice

First, if a climate policy can sometimes make a positive difference to addressing another problem then it does seem to be perverse to ignore that. Suppose one has two mitigation policies, A and B. Suppose also that A and B are both equally good at mitigating climate change but that A also helps address another issue (say poverty or malnutrition or disease) then it would be odd to ignore that and disregard that fact. Other things being equal, we should prefer A over B. Put another way: if one policy has greater 'co-benefits' than another it is very hard to conclude that that is irrelevant when determining which to implement.

The underlying principle here is that agents have a duty to further just outcomes. This principle can be endorsed from within a variety of different ethical traditions. It would, for example, be affirmed by:

- *consequentialist moralities*. Peter Singer famously argues that agents have duties to assist others in poverty or malnutrition if we can do so without having to make unreasonable sacrifices (Singer 1972).
- *rights based approaches*. The same conclusion would be reached by rights-based approaches such as that defended by Henry Shue. Shue argues that all persons have 'basic rights' to a decent minimum

quality of life (Shue 1980). These imply negative duties not to harm but they also entail positive duties to assist (Shue 1980, ch 2).

- *egalitarian approaches*. The same conclusion would also be affirmed by those who argue that global justice requires a more equal world (Caney 2005, ch 4).

This argument, then, gives us some reason to think that, in at least some circumstances, governments and other organizations should adopt climate policies that advance other important objectives (like development or gender equality or protecting biodiversity). So if we can adopt a mitigation policy that not only mitigates climate change but also additionally assists overcoming other injustices (for example, it enables people to develop) then we should do so.

§2. Political Feasibility and Linkages

A second reason for doing so concerns political feasibility. It is striking that when climate policies have been enacted within states they have generally succeeded because they have been linked with *other* issues – issues, for example, such as housing, jobs, clean air, energy security, housing, and land rights. To be politically successful climate policy needs the support of a broad coalition. Mitigation policies are unlikely to be supported on purely climate-based considerations. But they have sometimes been supported when they have been linked with other struggles against other injustices (Basseches et al 2022, esp 15-16; Cipler 2022, esp p.327; Roberts et al 2018, esp p.305).² To the extent that this is true, then, we have a second reason for crafting climate policies in ways that address other injustices too. The argument is that doing so can, *in some circumstances*, make climate policies more politically feasible. (I note a limitation to this argument below.)

§3. Dual (Multi-) Purpose Policymaking

There is a further point. Our question is whether climate policies should be designed to address other injustices and social evils. When considering this it is worth examining more closely what exactly is meant by a ‘climate policy’. Many might regard a carbon tax, for example, as a paradigmatic climate policy.

The situation is, however, more complicated. Consider the burning of fossil fuels. This can be framed in different ways: - (i) causing climate change, (ii) causing air pollution, (iii) providing a source of employment, and so on.

Given this, it can be a mistake to treat a policy instrument that is designed to reduce or eliminate the use of fossil fuels (such as, say, a carbon tax) as if it is *only* a climate *policy*. It might be a good policy (and it might be adopted) for a plurality of reasons. These might include (i) it mitigates climate change but also (ii) it reduces air pollution and thereby contributes to citizens’ health and general well-being.³ Or consider subsidizing renewables. This can be seen as (i) mitigating climate change, but also (ii) providing employment, and (iii) reducing reliance on hostile foreign states and so promoting rights of self-determination.

The point then is this: some of the policies one might designate “climate” policies can appropriately be designed to address other injustices because the phenomenon they are addressing (burning fossil fuels) generates a number of different injustices and the solution being proposed also addresses several injustices

² See also Stephens (2022).

³ The figures on this are striking. Vohra et al (2021) report that fossil-fuel caused fine particulate matter results in 8.7 million premature deaths per annum (p.5).

(thereby securing people's right to a stable and safe climate system, people's right to health and clean air, people's right to a job). In such cases it is appropriate to use a "climate" policy to realize other social objectives and address other injustices.

The upshot of these three arguments then is this: There can then be principled and practical reasons for crafting policies designed to mitigate (or enable adaptation to) climate change in ways that serve non-climate goals too.

IV: Limits

However, it would be a mistake to infer from these three reasons that we should require of all climate policies that they can or should solve all the world's evils. This is too heavy a burden to impose on them.

§1. Effectiveness

One explanation of this is that in many cases the best way of addressing another injustice normally lies with identifying and then tackling the root cause of that injustice. Consider, for example, unfair terms of trade that penalize developing countries. Or the use of tariffs to pressurize vulnerable countries to accede and comply with unjust demands. These are forms of global injustice, but it is hard to see why climate policy instruments would be an appropriate response, rather than addressing the root cause of the problem. Or consider unjust immigration laws. Again, these are a form of injustice but it is unclear why climate instruments would be the best response. Or consider the problems of "odious debt" (Jayachandran & Kremer 2006). Or consider now development. To the extent that poverty stems from the absence of "inclusive" political and economic institutions (Acemoglu & Robinson 2012) then the right remedy would seem to involve tackling these, rather than expecting climate policies to be able to resolve the problem. We have no reason to think that the policy instruments employed to mitigate and adapt to climate change are necessarily capable of effectively fully addressing all other injustices.⁴

§2. Overload

In addition to this, there is a risk of overload - of too many tasks being ascribed to climate institutions and multilateral processes (when the tasks should in many cases be addressed by other fora).

§3. Political Feasibility

Furthermore, while linking climate with other goals can *sometimes* enhance the political feasibility of climate goals (Caney 2012), that is not always the case. Some may be willing to endorse some climate policies, but only if they are not linked with certain other issues (and vice versa).

V: Where Does This Leave Us?

To summarize: I have argued that

[1] When designing climate policies it is wrong to bracket out all other non-climate issues (integrationism)

4 For further discussion see Posner and Weisbach (2010, chapter 4).

[2] There are three reasons to think that it is sometimes appropriate to design “climate policies” in ways that contribute to overcoming other kinds of injustices (such as poverty, malnutrition, biodiversity loss) – the *argument from positive duties*, the *argument from political feasibility*, and the *argument from multi-purpose policymaking*.

But

[3] There are important limits and we should not expect climate change policies to be the solution for all the world’s ills. There are many different kinds of global injustice. Addressing these requires addressing their root causes and there is no reason to think that the most effective and appropriate response to these will always necessarily involve climate policy instruments. Furthermore, to do so threatens to overload the political processes dedicated to tackling climate change. So we need to bear in mind the criteria of *effectiveness*, *overload* and *political feasibility*.

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Wielding the Narrative Knife: Open Questions for Climate Equity Analysts

During the 1930's the Dust Bowl swept through the western USA. This profound drought and soil erosion event covered 100 million acres, caused wide-spread human migration and suffering, and cost the equivalent of 570 US million (in 2024 dollars) a day by 1936. It fed domestic political turmoil, shaped bitter debates about the role of government in periods of upheaval and deep inequality, and forced a reckoning with the limits to human exploitation of ecological systems. In his essay reflecting on the stories told about the dust-bowl, the environmental historian William Cronon (1992) argues that “narratives remain our chief moral compass in the world. Because we use them to motivate and explain our actions, the stories we tell change the way we act in the world”. Without a narrator making decisions about what to share and what to hide, it would be impossible for us to navigate what would otherwise be a bewilderment of facts and observations. A narrative is ‘a telling,’ but it must obscure in order to tell. It cannot tell everything because we humans cannot process everything; what gets hidden is as central to its coherence as what is made visible. “Separating the story from the non-story” is, Cronon tells us, “the most powerful yet dangerous tool of the narrative form”.

The challenge, as Cronon himself was grappling with in the face of debates about appropriate governance¹ for a complex socio-economic, political and ecological crisis with the power to upend the notion of government itself, is that depending on the narrative arc being used, radically different notions of action emerge. Narratives have actors, including protagonists and villains, and plot lines that are generated by sculpting problems to which solutions are proposed or pursued. However, in a situation with many competing narratives, it is not obvious which ones should be relied on and which ones should not, or which information should be highlighted in our narrations and which can or should remain hidden. This challenge could not be more pointed for those of us providing analyses about equity and climate change. How ought we as analysts craft narratives (or models) in the climate equity context, bearing in mind that our decisions will shape all following notions of what various actors ought to do? In recognizing the flexibility of narrative, does anything go?

In reflecting on this problem, Cronon admits that he has re-written his essay four separate times because he does not know what to do with the fluid power of narratives. He finally proposes a set of three guidelines. First, our narratives cannot contradict known facts, and second, they must make ecological sense. As Cronon puts it, “nature coauthors our stories”. The third is that they must be created and evaluated as a product of a community, the members of which are empowered to critically engage with and challenge each other's narratives. In his words, “we tell stories with each other and against each other in order to speak to each other”. From this perspective a good narrative is one that enables real, critical communication amongst those involved in a decision-context.

We can apply these ideas to climate equity narratives to start identifying potential guidelines in this context. Specifically, these ideas would suggest that we must use solid climate science, recognize past factual actions that contributed to climate change, and account for the real consequences of both increased climate change

1 The central debate about governance to which he is referring is similar to those about governance and the interconnected climate-capital crisis today. The governance tension he is reflecting on is between those who see a strong government development agenda, represented as the New Deal (what would now be something akin to a Green New Deal in which government uses its power to attempt to achieve multiple sustainable development goals simultaneously), versus a move away from excessive government interference, regulation, and taxation burden (what would now be moves towards economic growth itself, without any modifiers or governmental restrictions, as the primary goal).

and climate policy actions. A narrative that failed to reflect past actions, or that left out climate impacts, or that glossed over the implications of particular policy approaches would start to deviate from a story that doesn't contradict facts and that is 'co-authored by nature.' Moreover, our narratives should be crafted in ways that facilitate deeper and sharper communication with our peers². We should be trying to 'speak to each other' with our narratives. In practice there could be several non-exclusive pathways for doing this.

One pathway would be to **focus narratives more specifically on underlying equity concerns** within the larger umbrella of climate and equity. The implicit argument here is that if left at a fairly abstract level, reliance on broad concepts like 'equity' or 'development' limits the quality of narratives because they lack sufficient detail to enable critical community reflection, can be easily manipulated,³ and can mask real issues of concern. Instead, leaning into the more particular messiness of real life could enable more productive dialogue: it may be more difficult to apply a standard set of equations across the board, but the contextualization may be worth it.

To make this more concrete, consider the difference between a narrative in which access to sustainable development is represented only by GDP per capita, and one in which several multi-dimensional metrics for development and poverty are used. The first can easily feed into general statements about global (in)equity but is less likely to be useful for identifying specific ways that climate action could be approached that enhances access to sustainable development. It also wouldn't facilitate meaningful debate about what is required by whom to achieve universal access to sustainable development. Instead, working to link what it actually means to have limited access to sustainable development to climate action options through the use of multi-dimension metrics and/or accounts of real people's lives when creating narratives is much more likely to help users find productive pathways forward. Reducing reliance on simplifications or flattened proxies that mask the lived realities embedded within all aspects of navigating the causes and effects of climate change may help avoid relatively thin and well-rehearsed equity exchanges, especially in the politically contested territory in which we work.

A second pathway would entail **being explicit about our use of the narrative knife: what we include, what we exclude, and why**. Several years ago, a proposal was made (Winkler and Klinky 2018) for using the concept of 'values-focused thinking' (Keeney 1992) in modeling efforts for climate equity. The idea was that articulating a set of dimensions across which insights would allow us to pose an ideal state for modeling equity against which we could then compare progress. The six dimensions needed to inform equity debates that we identified were: a) assess climate impacts, adaptation, loss and damage; b) be sensitive to context; c) compare costs of mitigation and adaptation policy action; d) incorporate multi-dimensional human development and poverty; d) integrate inequality dynamics; and f) be clear about normative assumptions and responsive to users. Any or all of these could be used as the focus of equity analyses. Actively being transparent about which of these are considered central and which are left out in, why these choices are made, and how (and why) they have been represented in practice could help facilitate the kind of community dialogue and assessment about the implications of the moral compass being used the Cronon

2 I'm being a little lazy here because I'm not sketching out how to define this community. This is important and speaks to the transparency/procedural justice value we identified in that paper and, if one thinks about extended peer review, a broad definition of community could force a significant change from much of the current work. However, because I have only 2 pages and this is already 3 I'm leaving it out.

3 Here I am thinking about the first time Donald Trump pulled the US out of Paris in which he strongly used notions of "fairness" in his speech to justify his action. He was less nuanced and more realpolitik the second time around, simply arguing that such international agreements were not in the interest of the American people, with essentially no consideration of fairness or equity at all.

had in mind. This strongly resonates with the calls others have made about the absolute necessity for clarity of assumptions in any equity modeling or narrative (Dooley et al. 2021).

A third pathway would be rigorous assessment of the extent to which narratives meet the first two of Cronon's guidelines: **do they resonate with facts, and do they make ecological sense?** While this sounds like perhaps the most pedestrian of the options, I'd suggest its far from it. It would require all of us doing any kind of analysis to take stock and revisit all of our assumptions about how we built our implicit or explicit narratives.

Let's take the issue of facts first. The obvious issue here is the question of which facts to include, which immediately manifests the core challenge of wielding the narrative knife. However, if we combine sensitivity about facts with an interest in greater specificity, we could think about what would happen if we included a greater range of core factors in our analyses of why emission and development trajectories have emerged the way they have, and with what implications. Here we would be effectively revisiting our narrative structure – who are the protagonists and the villains, what is the problem and why is it that way? For example, what if, when writing global narratives to explore just transitions for instance, we widened the focus (both historically and towards the future) from core metrics of fossil energy production and employment to include recognition of education systems, skills development, and rural economic change writ large (to name a few)? This would resonate with the range of decisions countries will actually have to make to advance a just transition, and opens the door to many more forms of international cooperation than might otherwise be visible. This would also pose real methodological challenges to many mainstream modeling efforts, especially at the global level, but if such models are not resonating with the facts that we think are most pertinent to, say, a story of what it would take to get a globally just transition, or what actual universal access to sustainable development in an era of climate change would require, then maybe such a rethink is in order.

The issue of making ecological sense also poses challenges to current norms within narratives and models for climate equity. Making ecological sense would demand that any analysis be explicit about climate impacts associated with any level of mitigation. The damage function has always been a challenge for modeling and often gets left out even in more narrative accounts of action. Strongly demanding that narratives and models make ecological sense reinforces the importance of taking these seriously. However, this would also encourage the integration of life-cycle analysis or other systems approaches when considering, for instance existing and proposed energy infrastructure, biofuels, or adaptation infrastructure. Perhaps most dramatically, this would require genuine ecological reckoning with underlying assumptions about infinite growth and/or business as usual, not only on the emissions front, but across all ecological systems. Stressing the need to make ecological sense is not to say that certain choices should not be made but that the ecological ramifications ought to be made clear in our tools of analysis, so that the model or narrative can be said to have been 'coauthored by nature'.

Nothing that Cronon argues is new, and nothing that I've suggested here is new. And yet, pausing to think about what a 'good' narrative is does offer a place from which to re-evaluate how we as analysts are wielding our tools of the trade. The elephant in the room as I've been writing this is, of course, the current political moment. This too is reminiscent of Cronon's reflection as the dust bowl narratives he was considering were written in a period of political turmoil⁴ in which people were looking for lines of thought that would help take them where they thought the world (or country) needed to go. As he writes, when "trying to understand the choices that confronted the people whose lives we narrate so as to capture the full tumult of their world" we

4 Cronon explicitly notes this issue – in his case the narratives he is evaluating were written after the Dust bowl but in another politically tumultuous era of the Reagan – Thatcher era in which there was wide spread debate about appropriate governance.

can see the dilemmas we ourselves face, “and at the intersection of the two we locate the moral of the story”. Perhaps the biggest choice we make is who our audience is, and what our assumptions are about why the world needs the narrative, or model, we are contributing. Here the core question also goes back to a central one for the narrative form – who are the protagonists and who are the villains, and what does our story arc assume has to happen to these actors to from here to where we think the world should go? Perhaps a place to start this conversation amongst a community of analysts committed to furthering some sense of climate equity is this, “right here, right now, what are the stories we need to explore and why”?

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Carbon dioxide removal (CDR) and equity

A brief explainer – what is the role of CDR in net-zero scenarios: The purpose of CDR as defined by IPCC is to – 1) counterbalance hard-to-abate residual GHG emissions; 2) achieve “net negative” emissions (to help reverse any temperature overshoot above 1.5°C). However, removals must be permanently stored away from the atmosphere for CDR to counterbalance or remove emissions from fossil fuels (geological net zero), meaning one tonne of CO₂ permanently restored to the solid Earth for every tonne still generated from fossil sources.¹ Yet the majority of current, pledged and modelled CDR is based on enhancing terrestrial sinks or carbon neutrality assumptions for bioenergy

This briefing is divided into 4 sections – 1) the scale of (current, pledged and modelled) CDR deployment; 2) the impacts of this deployment; 3) proposed limits to CDR; and 4) equity considerations, before posing questions for discussion.

Scale of CDR in scenarios

Current deployment of CDR is reported by the global carbon budget² as the removal component of the net anthropogenic land flux, which averaged 1.8 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ over the past decade, with an additional 0.203 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ removals from wood products, BECCS and wetlands.³ However, this is occurring in the context of emissions of about 7 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ from deforestation, leading to a global net flux from land use that is a source of around 5 Gt CO₂y⁻¹.²

CDR in existing climate pledges is also high, with governments heavily relying on CDR to reach net zero. Removals of up to 5 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ are included in 2050 climate pledges, the majority of which is conventional CDR on land.⁴ The potential demand for additional land to achieve CDR in NDCs and 2050 climate pledges is estimated at approximately 1 billion hectares, with half of this for tree-planting and reforestation.⁵

Estimates for future CDR potential scale up significantly from current deployment. IPCC AR6 assessed CDR potential in two main ways: the technical potential, defined as “the biophysical potential or amount possible with current technologies” and the economic potential, defined as the technical potential “constrained by costs, usually by a given carbon price”.⁶ p.774 The global technical potential for land-based, primarily quantified using “sectoral” assessments, is given as 28.4 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ in 2050, while the economic potential, primarily quantified using integrated assessment models (IAMs), is given as 7.9 Gt CO₂ in 2050. In 2100, this rises to 15.4 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ in scenarios that return warming to 1.5°C after a high overshoot, compared with 11.4 Gt CO₂y⁻¹ in scenarios without overshoot.⁷ The difference between technical and economic CDR potentials is principally attributed to IAMs capturing competition for land between different CDR practices.⁷

IAMs and overshoot – what drives scale of CDR in models? The concept of CDR is very closely tied to overshoot (the more CDR a model has in it, the higher and longer the overshoot generally is), hence emission reductions in the coming decade substantially determine the magnitude of removals required in subsequent decades.⁸ More than two-thirds of pathways (436 of 648 scenarios) assessed in the AR6 that return warming to 1.5°C by the end of this century involve some overshoot and net-negative CO₂ emissions after 2050.⁹

Assumptions in models that drive CDR include assumed economic growth (in the range of 2.5 to 3.5% per year until 2050)⁶ (footnote 46) and including the cost of mitigation measures but not climate impacts.⁶ High discount rates, used to compare costs in models across time, push action further into the future. Emmerling et al¹⁰ found that halving the discount rate roughly halved the rate of CDR deployment in models. CDR is

selected in modelled scenarios based on least-cost mitigation options, meaning that CDR can ‘outcompete’ other uses of land based on carbon price, unless external constraints are applied. Model assumptions related to crop yields, available land, conversion efficiency of biomass to energy, etc, also drive CDR uptake.⁷

Impacts from CDR

Widespread concerns have been raised about the impacts of CDR on human and Indigenous peoples’ rights, food security, biodiversity, natural ecosystems.^{7,11-15} The potential adverse impacts from CDR derive from two aspects – the deployment of CDR itself, and the length and intensity of overshoot.

In terms of deployment - the scale of CDR in modelled scenarios implies changes in rates of land use that are unprecedented in human history,¹⁶ with clear implications for planetary boundaries,¹⁴ food security¹⁷ and human rights. The increase in land for BECCS and afforestation comes at the expense of grasslands, pasture and production of cereal crops.¹⁸ One 1.5C scenario which included Direct Air Capture (DAC) to reduce the reliance on land (and restricted expansion of BECCS and afforestation into natural lands) found that CDR required resulted in staple food crop prices rising by approximately fivefold relative to 2010 levels in many parts of the Global South.¹⁵ An assessment of impacts on agriculture predicted a 12.8% reduction in global cropland area when accounting for cross-sectoral impacts of climate pledges and land-use intensity, with the global south comprising 81% of the countries expected to experience cropland loss.¹⁹

Overshoot brings substantial equity concerns, for example related to unequally distributed, and sometimes irreversible, impacts of climate change if warming surpasses 1.5°C, even temporarily, including damage to ecosystems and greater loss of human life.²⁰ Climate breakdown also magnifies existing social inequities, as those with the fewest resources, such as impoverished peoples and historically marginalized and oppressed groups, are especially vulnerable to climate damages,²⁰ including the irreversible harm caused by an overshoot of 1.5°C.

Limits to CDR

A crucial question is how much CDR can be deployed sustainably. The mitigation potential for CDR reported by the IPCC has been primarily constrained by techno-economic considerations, but has been lacking the assessment of feasibility (socio-cultural, environmental, and institutional factors).

Proposals for a CDR budget understand CDR as a fundamentally finite resource. Deprez et al²¹ assess sustainability risks associated with land-use change and biodiversity loss from CDR and recommend the need to estimate a sustainable CDR budget based on socioecological thresholds, which would then require allocating limited CDR supply to the most legitimate uses. Following this, Caldecott and Johnstone²² suggest a CDR budget as a tool to help forecast supply and demand for CDR. This approach applies a technology readiness level to CDR potentials and accounts for CDR used and CDR required to meet a given temperature target over time. Hence, while the concept adds a temporal dimension (as technology is developed, scaled up and deployed), it does not advance current understanding of feasibility constraints beyond AR6.

Different modelling approaches – Perkins et al⁷ propose a transdisciplinary approach for improving understanding of feasibility constraints on land-based CDR, with approaches that offer improved modelling of human behaviour including combining optimization-based approaches (i.e., IAMs) with externally defined constraints on rates of land-use change;²³ explicit process representation using agent-based models (ABMs); spatial simulation-based approaches;²⁴ or quantifying environmental constraints to CDR uptake using stylized scenarios in dynamic global vegetation models (DGVMs).^{14,25} Such constraints could be used to

provide environmental limits on CDR adoption in both optimization-based and simulation based land-use models.

Legal limits to CDR – a growing body of research documents legal limits to the use of CDR. Stuart-Smith et al⁸ argue that climate targets that depend heavily on CO₂ removal may contravene norms and principles of international law. This work primarily rests on the argument of risks caused by excessive reliance on CDR: risks of nondeployment of CDR due to uncertainty (technological, legal, social, economic); non-permanence of storage, particularly for terrestrial CDR; risks of adverse social, economic, and environmental impacts from CDR deployment; and elevated climate change impacts due to overshoot. Previous work presented a similar risk-based analysis of CDR,^{7,13} or emphasises the moral hazard of relying on CDR.²⁶

Stuart-Smith offer a framework for assessing the legality of emissions pathways that depend on CDR, based on the need for mitigation pathways to be scientifically sound, to be compatible with a human rights approach to achieving climate goals, and to consider intergenerational equity. A key barrier to imposing legal limits on CDR is that pledges for net-zero are rarely transparent about the extent and geographical and technological makeup of reliance on CDR to meet climate targets.

Equity considerations

Who is responsible for deploying CDR, paying for it, and with what consequences? The opportunity and obligation to undertake CDR are not equally distributed amongst actors and geographies.

Most of the literature addressing the equity considerations of CDR has framed CDR as a burden-sharing problem, suggesting a **fair shares approach** to CDR deployment at the scale implied by IAM cost-optimisation approaches. One approach, using **responsibility and capacity** to distribute the CDR burden between nations results in 2–3 times larger CDR responsibilities for the United States, the European Union and China compared with a global least-cost approach.²⁷ This compares approaches based on cumulative per capita emissions' (with a 1990 baseline) and an ability to pay approach (wealthier states take more responsibility) to a least cost CDR distribution. Cumulative per capita increases US and EU share, while ability to pay increases China's responsibility and decreases US.²⁷

A proposal to allocate responsibility based on **the polluter pays principle** suggests fossil fuel producers have a “carbon takeback obligation”.²⁸ This would see fossil fuel companies take responsibility for CDR, through an obligation to pay for an equivalent amount of future CDR removal for every further tonne of CO₂ they emit. As obligation for carbon takeback rises, costs will be passed onto consumers, reducing willingness to pay for fossil fuel products. This expected price elasticity is the only mechanism whereby fossil fuel production is actually reduced in this proposal. Others argue for treating CDR as a **public good**, akin to waste disposal, given that CO₂ is a waste product of combusting fossil fuels, and its accumulation in the atmosphere presents a planetary hazard.²⁹

Potential topics for discussion could be:

The role CDR plays in limiting warming in modelled scenarios and how to address optimistic IAM assessments to better represent sustainable limits for CDR.

The modelled scenarios in IPCC assessments are contingent on highly contested economic assumptions and policy choices. By excluding the costs of climate impacts and adaptation, and the economic co-benefits of mitigation, assuming continued economic growth and using high discount rates, scenarios bias towards including CDR. Of the 1,686 assessed scenarios, only 97 limit warming to 1.5°C with no or low overshoot. What

role can different modelling approaches, different economic assumptions, or alternative approaches play in assessing CDR feasibility?

The equity implications of CDR.

The literature so far on equity and CDR mostly focuses on equitable distribution of CDR costs and implementation, without engaging with the underlying economic assumptions that constrain mitigation choices. How can considerations of equity add to the understanding of the role of CDR in mitigation scenarios, including questions of scale, feasibility, geographic and temporal distribution?

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Equity and fairness in the distribution of gains from decarbonization

Climate and energy policies will inevitably create winners and losers, as the costs and benefits of transitioning to a low-carbon economy are unevenly distributed. Academic studies and policy debates especially in the “just transitions” context have typically focused on the “losers” – those sectors, regions, or groups that would bear the adverse consequences of mitigation policies. Models have often been used to analyze trade-offs and highlight costs for vulnerable industries or communities. For example, models project reductions in GDP or income in certain sectors and regions under climate policy scenarios. By breaking down impacts by industry or geographic region, models can identify who would bear disproportionate burdens – for example, energy-intensive industries facing higher operating costs, fossil-fuel producing regions seeing declines in output, or households paying higher energy prices. In the context of climate change mitigation, “losers” came to denote actors adversely affected by the transition (even if society overall gains).

These insights into who loses can enable policymakers to anticipate trade-offs – for example, which industries might shrink or which regions might experience job losses – and to prepare transition plans or compensation. The historical approach in both research and policy design was often **“Who gets hurt by this policy, by how much, and how can we ease that pain?”** Politically, this was (and remains) critical: if the pain of climate policy falls on a concentrated few, those few can become powerful opponents. Research has shown that groups expecting to lose tend to mobilize against policy unless they anticipate compensation. In short, addressing losers was seen as a prerequisite for ambitious climate action. Consequently, most just transition narratives center on mitigating harms to affected workers and regions.

However, decarbonization will also produce “winners” – sectors, regions and groups that will gain from the growth in development and deployment of low carbon technologies in the energy and industrial sectors. In many countries, industrial and economic policy has focused specifically on capturing some of these gains, for example through policies to support domestic manufacturing (domestic content mandates) or policies to support technology development and the creation of IP.

The IRA in the US was sold as an inflation reduction and industrial revival plan, even as it contained provisions to ensure benefits reach disadvantaged groups. However, as Lewis (2024) points out, the IRA does not include any provisions for addressing potential (negative) spillovers on developing countries.¹

The EU’s Green Deal also frames climate action as a “new growth strategy” for Europe, presented as a driver of innovation, economic opportunity, and improved quality of life. On the international stage, the EU has promoted the idea of “sharing the benefits of a green economy transition” globally, not just the burdens (IPCC AR6 WG3 Ch. 15). Many countries’ climate plans now come with job estimates and health impact estimates. For example, India’s renewable energy expansion is justified not only on energy security but also on the millions of green jobs it could create and the reduced smog in cities. China, in its 14th Five-Year Plan and carbon neutrality pledges, often highlights the opportunity to become a global leader in clean tech manufacturing – meaning economic winners domestically.

Critical minerals (and securing supply chains for those minerals) is being seen as a matter of national security for many governments. To date, much of the supply chain work has studied how developed countries like the US and EU, which have the market power, but not enough natural resources for the critical minerals, can secure these minerals for their markets. In conjunction, many of the policies on critical minerals are focused

1 Joanna I. Lewis; The Climate Risk of Green Industrial Policy. *Current History* 1 January 2024; 123 (849): 14–19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1525/curh.2024.123.849.14>

on securing the supply for consumption in these markets. There is very limited work on how developing countries, like the DRC, which are resource-rich but energy access-poor, can leverage these resources effectively to drive energy access and economic growth – and how global climate policies could support this process.

As mitigation policies emphasize aspects such as competitiveness and job creation in the new climate economy, it becomes increasingly important to examine issues of equity and fairness regarding these opportunities. Can (or how can) a cleaner and low-carbon world also become a fairer and more equitable world? How can the wealth creation that will necessarily accompany any large-scale system transition be more equitably distributed?

There is emerging literature on the distribution of gains. For example, Kennedy et al (2024) note that high-income countries are increasingly taking a domestic-first approach to associated economic benefits – leaving the local economic benefits to low- and middle-income producer countries unclear.²

However, significant gaps remain in how current models and policies integrate the analysis of winners (benefits) into climate policy design. Historically, analytical tools and decision frameworks were skewed toward costs; rebalancing them to fully account for benefits is an ongoing challenge. Key gaps include:

- Limited integration of Co-benefits in integrated models
- Co-Benefit distribution often assessed externally in stand-alone studies and fragmented analyses
- Insufficient Granularity for Equity Analysis, regional, sectoral & within-country
- Challenges in valuing and comparing diverse benefits, including gaps in well-being measurement
- Much focus has been on domestic distribution, but a gap remains in ensuring global sharing of benefits.
- Dynamic & long-term uncertainty in accounting for how benefits and winners might evolve over time

This suggests a number of relevant policy and research questions:

- who gains (between countries and within countries) and how much?
- how is value distributed in the clean energy value chain? A lot of the literature on critical minerals focuses on securing the supply chain - but how can energy-poor but resource rich countries gain equitably and sustainably from their resources?
- how do we think about equity and fairness regarding gains? There are many approaches for thinking about equity in the context of the distribution of the mitigation burden. What about equity regarding the distribution of economic rents or the gains from trade?
- how do we model and assess these gains? For example, how can supply-chain analyses and other interdisciplinary approaches (e.g., socio-economic impact analyses, labor market studies) enhance our understanding of the distributional dynamics associated with policy-induced benefits?

2 Kennedy, K. M., Borrero, M. A., Edwards, M. R., O'Rourke, P., Hultman, N. E., & Surana, K. (2024). Advancing equitable value chains for the global hydrogen economy. *Energy and Climate Change*, 5, 100166.